

Efficient trustworthy AI - making the best of data (AI, Data and Robotics Partnership)
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PANDORA

A Comprehensive Framework enabling the Delivery of
Trustworthy Datasets for Efficient AIoT Operation

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List of Abbreviations

3DGS – 3D Gaussian Splatting
ADL – Activities of Daily Living
AI – Artificial Intelligence
AIoT – Artificial Intelligence of Things
ALTAI – Assessment List for Trustworthy AI
BNNs – Bayesian Neural Networks
CA – Consortium Agreement
CIL – Class-Incremental Learning
CINs – Continual Inference Networks
CNNs – Convolutional Neural Networks
DAGs – Directed Acyclic Graphs
DMD – Dynamic Mode Decomposition
DL – Deep Learning
EC – European Commission
FL – Federated Learning
FRL – Federated Representation Learning
GAN – Generative Adversarial Networks
GBMs – Gradient Boosting Machines
GDPR – General Data Protection Regulation
GENEOs – Group Equivariant Non-Expansive Operators
GPs – Gaussian Processes
HALP – Host-Assisted Layer-wise Parallelization
ICA – Independent Component Analysis
IG – Integrated Gradients
IoT – Internet of Things
kNN – k-Nearest Neighbors
LLMs – Large Language Models
LOCF – Last Observation Carried Forward
MCMC – Markov Chain Monte Carlo
MICE – Multivariate Imputation by Chained Equation
MLP – Multi-Layer Perceptron
MVI – Missing Value Inference
ND – Novelty Detection
NDA – Non-Disclosure Agreement
NIDS – Network Intrusion Detection Systems
NMPC – Nonlinear Model Predictive Control
NOCB – Next Observation Carried Backward
ns-3 – Network Simulator 3

OOD – Out of Data Distribution
OSR – Open Set Recognition
PCA – Principal Component Analysis
PM – Predictive Maintenance
RFS – Receptive Field-Based Segmentation
RL – Representational Learning
RNNs – Recurrent Neural Networks
SB – Scientific Board
SfM – Structure-from-Motion
SotA – State of the Art
SVD – Singular Value Decomposition
t-SNE – t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding
TDA – Topological Data Analysis
TSVS – Time Series Variable Selection
VAEs – Variational Autoencoders
XAI – Explainable AI
xAD – Explainable Anomaly Detection
xTSC – Explainable Multivariate Time Series Classification

Executive Summary

This specific deliverable outlines the foundational aspects of the PANDORA project, a European Union initiative aimed at advancing the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) with the Internet of Things (IoT), referred to as AIoT. The project's objective is to enhance IoT applications by embedding AI capabilities, allowing devices not only to collect and transmit data but also to analyze, learn, and respond intelligently. This integration aims to revolutionize various industries by improving decision-making, fostering seamless human-machine interaction, and streamlining operations.

Key elements of the PANDORA setup include:

- **Definition of AIoT:** Highlighting how AIoT enables devices with sensing, processing, and communication capabilities to interact with their environment more intelligently, allowing them to execute complex tasks autonomously.
- **Project Objectives and Scope:** PANDORA is structured to address multiple research areas, including data generation, uncertainty quantification, and explainable AI, which will contribute to creating a resilient and ethical AIoT framework.
- **Multidisciplinary Research:** The project establishes a collaborative structure involving research in fields like federated learning, adaptive AI, and self-learning algorithms to tackle the challenges of reliable, secure, and adaptable AI systems for IoT environments. The setup includes a Scientific Board to ensure the research is aligned with high standards.
- **Legal and Ethical Considerations:** Compliance with EU regulatory standards (such as the AI Act) and data privacy regulations is emphasized. The project framework integrates rigorous cybersecurity measures and ethical guidelines to meet the challenges posed by autonomous AI systems, such as transparency and user privacy.
- **Future Impact:** The expected outcomes include improved operational efficiency and AI-driven intelligence in IoT systems, ultimately providing a foundation for smart applications across domains like smart cities, healthcare, and industrial automation.

The document underscores PANDORA's commitment to pushing the boundaries of AIoT by developing scalable, secure, and ethically sound AI technologies tailored to IoT ecosystems.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of the deliverable is to establish the foundational structure and operational guidelines for the PANDORA project. This includes defining the project's objectives, methodologies, and key components. Specifically, the deliverable aims to:

- **Outline Project Objectives and Framework:** Set the scope, goals, and strategic direction for PANDORA, focusing on integrating AI with IoT (AIoT) to enhance the functionality and decision-making capabilities of IoT devices.
- **Define Collaborative Research Structure:** Establish a multidisciplinary approach involving partners across various fields, ensuring that scientific and technological efforts align with the project's objectives.
- **Address Compliance and Ethical Standards:** Document and implement measures for adherence to EU regulatory standards, including data privacy, cybersecurity, and ethical guidelines to build trustworthiness in AI systems.
- **Identify Related Research and Assets:** Integrate knowledge and tools from previous EU-funded initiatives, setting a collaborative groundwork for using existing resources to accelerate progress.

This deliverable thus serves as a comprehensive project setup document, guiding the consortium in achieving project goals while ensuring compliance and ethical alignment.

1.2 Definition of AIOT

The Internet of Things (IoT) has revolutionized the way we interact with the world [Q24] by connecting billions of devices such as smartphones, wearable devices, drones, and smart speakers. These devices, equipped with sensing, processing, networking, and communication capabilities, collect, analyze, and transmit a wide range of data, including images, videos, audio, text, wireless signals, and physiological signals from individuals and the physical world [S24]. However, the growing complexity of IoT and the need for more sophisticated data analysis have highlighted the limitations of traditional IoT systems [Za24].

The integration of IoT with artificial intelligence (AI), particularly deep learning, has given rise to a new paradigm known as the **Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT)** [Za24] [AIoTCon21]. AIoT aims to enhance IoT capabilities by integrating advanced AI algorithms, enabling devices to not only collect and transmit data but also to perceive, learn, reason, and behave intelligently.

AIoT is based on three key components: sensing, processing, and networking and communication:

Sensing: AIoT utilizes a variety of onboard sensors, such as cameras, microphones, motion, and physiological sensors, to gather data from individuals and the physical world. This data is then processed by modern AI algorithms for a variety of tasks such as classification, localization, anomaly detection, and many others.

Processing: AIoT focuses on AI-oriented processing tasks, using advanced AI algorithms to analyze the data collected by sensors and extract meaningful information. This processing can occur on devices, on the edge, or in the cloud, depending on application requirements.

Networking and Communication: The networking and communication component of AIoT ensures reliable transmission of sensor data and/or computed results to the cloud, to the edge, or to other nearby AIoT devices.

The significance of AIoT stems from its ability to improve decision-making, enhance human-machine interactions, and facilitate more efficient operations. By enabling billions of everyday devices with advancements made by modern AI, AIoT has the potential to radically transform how people perceive and interact with the world.

1.3 Intended readership

The intended readership for the deliverable includes:

- Project Consortium Members: Researchers, technical staff, and project managers from partner organizations within the PANDORA consortium, who need a clear understanding of the project structure, objectives, and operational guidelines.
- EU Project Officers: European Union representatives overseeing the project to ensure compliance with funding and regulatory requirements.
- AI and IoT Research Community: Scholars and developers in the fields of Artificial Intelligence and Internet of Things interested in the innovative integration and ethical frameworks proposed by PANDORA.
- Industry Stakeholders: Organizations and businesses in technology and AIoT sectors looking to align with cutting-edge advancements in AI and IoT integration and gain insights into ethical AI applications.
- Regulatory and Standards Bodies: EU regulatory entities and standards organizations focused on AI ethics, data privacy, and cybersecurity, who might consider PANDORA's methodologies and findings for informing or revising guidelines.

This readership list ensures that all key stakeholders are considered, facilitating both effective internal communication and alignment with broader EU objectives and industry standards.

1.4 Relationship with other PANDORA WPs and managerial organization

The relationship of the deliverable with other Work Packages (WPs) and the management organization in the project is foundational, supporting coordination across multiple areas and preparing a robust framework for further developments:

- WP1: D2.1 is closely tied to WP1, which oversees the project's overall management and coordination. WP1 provides essential infrastructure for the project's operations. D2.1, as part of WP2, aligns with WP1 by establishing the preliminary setup, setting out project governance frameworks, and defining initial procedural structures that WP1 will continuously manage and monitor.
- WP3: The initial groundwork in D2.1 helps ensure that WP3's research in data trustworthiness aligns with the ethical and technical benchmarks set during the project's setup phase.
- WP4: D2.1 supports WP4 by laying out a framework that considers ongoing requirements for sustainable and autonomous AIoT operations. WP4's focus on creating resilient AIoT systems relies on D2.1's preparatory work, which outlines technical standards and initial guidelines for system integration and performance metrics.
- WP5: D2.1's establishment of ethical, legal, and technical guidelines serves as a basis for WP5's development of data pipelines. WP5 can leverage these initial configurations to ensure data handling components align with the trustworthiness goals outlined in the setup phase.
- WP6: WP6 depends on the foundational setup in D2.1 for conducting real-life experiments. D2.1 provides a framework for validation, ethics, and compliance, essential for WP6's

testing against industry standards and assessing AIoT systems' performance under real-world conditions.

- WP7: WP7 is influenced by D2.1 through initial setup activities that establish communication channels and governance structures. This relationship ensures effective dissemination, international collaboration, and long-term sustainability, particularly by engaging stakeholders and aligning with European initiatives from the onset.

2. Related Initiatives and Assets

Extensive mapping of relevant projects and scientific assets from EU-funded past and ongoing initiatives has been carried out to effectively integrate knowledge and resources within the framework of PANDORA. This will identify scientific assets that include tools, technologies, knowledge, and skills developed during previous and ongoing EU-funded projects. Thereby, it also furthers a collaborative scientific environment in which insights from diverging disciplines can effectively be brought into the PANDORA framework to enable swifter progress. A comprehensive list of EU-funded projects and Assets relevant to the objectives of the PANDORA framework has been compiled into two key tables: Projects and Assets.

For completeness, the full details have been placed in tables included in the **Appendix**. The Projects table lists relevant EU-funded projects in which the project partners are involved: it represents a repository for bridge identification tools, methodologies, and systems that will enrich the PANDORA framework. Additionally, related strategies and tasks are mapped within the table for each project, providing WP Leaders with a useful reference for further information.

The Assets table lists the scientific resources in terms of research papers, datasets, and software providing substantial inputs and data for achieving framework's objectives and they are sorted based on the related strategy. Furthermore, the reference of the related strategies is significant to provide the Task/Strategy Leaders with a useful reference for further information.

3. Multidisciplinary research activities and Scientific Board

Task 2.2 started at month 1 of the project and lasted until month 4. Its main objective was to establish the scientific board of PANDORA. While the board establishment was completed within this task, its operation and activities will continue during the whole project duration. The Task 2.2 contributors' activities that supported the establishment of the scientific board included email communications, online meetings (including regular bi-weekly meetings of WP2), and discussions at the PANDORA technical meeting in Amsterdam at month 3.

The role of the scientific board is to monitor and give advice and feedback on the scientific aspects (activities, results, outcomes) of the project.

The board consists of internal and external members. Internal members are experts from the PANDORA consortium; external members are experts outside of the PANDORA consortium. The board is chaired by Prof. Georgios Bouloukakis (IMT), the PANDORA technical lead.

The process of establishment of the scientific board was as follows. Initial discussions took place among the project coordinator (NTUA), technical coordinator (IMT), Task 2.2 lead (UNSPMF), and Task 2.2 contributors (DIE, STUBA, IDC) regarding the board structure and members. It has been agreed that the internal board members be the following persons:

- Georgios Bouloukakis (IMT)
- Dusan Jakovetic (UNSPMF)
- Alexandros Iosifidis (AU)
- Konstantinos Tserpes (NTUA)

Once the internal board members were defined, the process of external board members had been initiated. Each internal board member institution and each Task 2.2 contributor institution proposed expert candidates for the external board. The final list of members has been selected by taking into account the multidisciplinary expertise of the external members as well as their relevance to PANDORA. The process resulted with the following list of external board members:

- Soumya Kar (Carnegie Mellon University, USA); expertise: distributed optimization and learning/AI, power networks and smart energy systems
- Yehia Elkhatib (University of Glasgow, UK); systems deployment
- Cheng-Hsin Hsu (National Tsing Hua University); IoT systems and multimedia
- Victor Sancez (Warwick University UK); machine learning and computer vision
- Davide Bacciu (University of Pisa); deep learning and generative models
- Peter Kertys (Slovenske elektrane); AI for nuclear power systems
- Patrick van der Smagt (ETAMI – Big Data Value Association (BDVA), Volkswagen AG, ELTE University); trustworthy AI.

The above proposal for the internal and external members of the scientific board was discussed at the project technical meeting in Amsterdam in month 3 and has been accepted by the full consortium.

A non-disclosure agreement (NDA) has been prepared by the project coordinator and accepted and signed by the signatories defined in the project's CA and the members of the SB. The former are EAB, SAG and PCL representing their own organizations and NTUA on behalf of the rest of the consortium members. The SB members signed as individuals rather than as representatives of their organizations.

The objective of the meetings is to receive feedback from the external EAB members on 1) relevant technologies that PANDORA may re-use (and use this feedback for potential improvement of D2.1); and 2) on the ambition (SotA) gaps that PANDORA identified (and use this feedback for potential improvement of D2.1); and 3) present PANDORA architecture and receive feedback (and use it for potential improvement of D2.2).

The first activity planned for the scientific board was an online meeting involving the internal board members, the PANDORA consortium, and the external board members, which took place during the last week of October 2024. This was the first focused meeting with EAB members with targeted scientific feedback required.

4. Literature Review

4.1 Introduction

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT), collectively known as the Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT), is revolutionizing the way we interact with technology and data. AIoT systems leverage the vast amounts of data generated by IoT devices, applying sophisticated AI algorithms to extract valuable insights, automate processes, and enhance decision-making capabilities. However, the success of AIoT applications is fundamentally dependent on the quality, reliability, and trustworthiness of the datasets they utilize.

This literature review aims to provide a comprehensive examination of the current state-of-the-art approaches in creating and managing trustworthy datasets for AIoT applications. The review is structured in two main sections:

- Cutting-edge techniques for the creation and management of trustworthy datasets.
- Challenges and solutions in the continual deployment of AIoT solutions and explainable behavior.

This document covers the following topics:

Synthetic Data Generation: This section explores methodologies for generating synthetic data, which can augment real-world datasets to address issues such as data scarcity, privacy concerns, and the need for diverse training datasets. We will discuss both simulation-based and machine learning-based approaches, highlighting their respective advantages and limitations.

Uncertainty Quantification: Understanding and managing uncertainty in AI models is crucial, especially in high-stakes applications. This section delves into the theoretical foundations of uncertainty in machine learning, distinguishing between aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty. It reviews key methods for uncertainty quantification, including Bayesian Neural Networks, ensemble methods, and credal networks, and discusses their applications in AIoT.

Explainable AI: As AI systems become more complex, the need for transparency and explainability grows. This section examines techniques for making AI models more interpretable, focusing on the integration of domain knowledge and the use of geometrical symmetries, as well as on the continuous character of the data. Explainable AI is essential for building trust with users and ensuring that AI decisions can be understood and validated.

Data Annotation and Labeling: High-quality labeled data is the backbone of supervised machine learning. This section reviews methods for automating the annotation and labeling process, reducing the labor-intensive nature of this task. It covers human-machine collaboration approaches, active learning, and the use of large language models for text annotation, emphasizing the importance of accurate and efficient data labeling.

Data Augmentation: To improve the robustness and generalization of AI models, data augmentation techniques are employed. This section discusses various augmentation methods for different data types, including images, text, graphs, tabular data, and time-series data. Data augmentation helps create more diverse and representative training datasets, enhancing model performance.

Techniques for Data Summarization, Dimensionality Reduction, and Fusion: Managing large and complex datasets requires effective techniques for summarization and dimensionality reduction. This section explores methods such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Independent Component Analysis (ICA), and t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE). It also discusses feature importance and autoencoders for feature extraction and data fusion, highlighting their role in simplifying data representation and improving computational efficiency.

Resilient Learning Strategies for Sustained Intelligence: In the data-centric AI era, collecting data and improving its quality is of critical importance for predictive models based on machine/deep learning techniques. This section addresses the challenges of noisy and missing data, and the importance of resilient machine learning algorithms that can handle out-of-distribution data instances and anomalies.

Continuous Self-Validated Learning for Improved Long-Term Autonomy and Intelligence: Continual learning provides a foundation for ML-based systems to develop adaptively. This section discusses the challenges of catastrophic forgetting and the need for balancing plasticity and stability in continual learning models. It also highlights the importance of self-validation in machine learning systems.

Federated Representational Learning for Efficient Data Formats: Federated learning (FL) has emerged as a decentralized learning paradigm for training machine learning models across multiple clients (edge nodes). This section explores the benefits of FL, including increased security and privacy, and the challenges of model aggregation and personalization.

Continuous Inference Networks for Faster Deep Learning Model Processing: Efficient methods have been proposed to optimize the process of sequential data analysis through Deep Learning models. This section discusses the advantages of Continual Inference Networks (CINs) for real-time processing of sequential data without computational redundancy.

Adaptive Distribution and Optimization of AI Inference Using Cloud-Edge Integration: The integration of cloud and edge computing has emerged as a robust solution to meet the computational challenges posed by AI inference tasks. This section explores model adaptation techniques, including model compression and conditional computation, to optimize AI workloads across the cloud-edge continuum.

By examining these approaches, the literature review aims to identify the strengths, limitations, and potential research gaps that need to be addressed to advance the field of AIoT. The insights gained from this review will inform the development of more reliable, efficient, and trustworthy AIoT systems, ultimately enhancing their impact across various applications. This comprehensive understanding of the current methodologies will serve as a foundation for future innovations and improvements in AIoT data management practices.

4.2 State-of-the-Art approaches for customizable and trustworthy datasets

4.2.1 Synthetic Data Generation Approaches for Trustworthy AIoT Applications

In the context of synthetic data generation for the IoT related field, we can categorize the relevant approaches into two main types: 1) *Simulation Approaches*, which simulate the behavior and interactions of IoT devices and systems, and 2) *Machine Learning Approaches*, which directly build models to learn data patterns of IoT devices or combine simulations with machine learning to enhance and optimize other methods. On the other hand, it is essential to consider the different types of data in IoT systems when generating synthetic data. We categorize IoT systems into 3 levels: *device*, *network* and *application*. The device level involves devices such as sensors and actuators, the network level focuses on the communication infrastructure, and the application level utilizes data for specific tasks, enabling intelligent applications that optimize operations or enhance user experiences. Table 1 outlines the different types of data at each level.

Table 1: Overview of Data Types and Characteristics

Data Level	Data type	Granularity	Scale
Device	Time-series labels [ZP21] [O20]	For energy efficiency datasets, each data point per day, for robot datasets each data point per 10ms.	Typically under 1000 timesteps for one sample of time series.
	Image [KNHnd] [DDS09]	For low resolution, typically 32x32, for high resolution images, typically 1024x1024.	For small-scale general datasets, around millions, for large-scale general datasets over hundred million.
	Video [S12] [KCS17]	For low resolution, around 300x200, for high resolution, over 500x500, over 25 framerates according to camera device.	Varies from around ten thousand videos to millions.
	Point Cloud [GLS13] [GLU12]	For self-driving datasets around 10 points per m ² , for high precision sensor datasets one point per cm ² .	Usually from thousands of points to a hundred million per frame for thousands of frames.
	3D Models [RKY23] [SSS06] [CFG15]	For low-resolution models, typically represented by a few thousand polygons, for high-resolution models, granularity can go down to voxel/pixel level.	Small-scale datasets typically consist of thousands of 3D models, large-scale datasets may consist of millions of models.
Network	Time series [M19] [ZTG21]	In network intrusion datasets, varies due to connection status, from 10ms per packet to several seconds	Contains thousands of log and network packets.
	Latency [HPW22] [TAE20]	In robotic communication datasets, vary due to connection status, from 10ms per packet to several seconds, for communication evaluating datasets, under 100ms.	In robotic communication datasets and evaluation datasets, vary from several milliseconds to several seconds due to communication status.
	Throughput [HPW22]	Varies due to connection status, from 10ms per packet to several seconds.	For robotic datasets around 10 kilobytes.
	SNR (Signal-to-Noise Ratio) [HPW22] [TAE20]	For robot datasets, from 10ms per packet to several seconds depending on connection status; For communication evaluation datasets, under 100ms.	Typically, around 10 dB, minimum for -20dB.
	RSSI (Received Signal Strength Indicator) [HPW22]	For robot datasets, from 10ms per packet to several seconds depending on connection status.	Typically, around -10 dBm, with variance for several dBm.
Application	Attacking label Time series [M19] [ZTG21]	Labeled for each timestep for attacking and intrusion detection dataset.	Typically, around ten thousand data samples several days.
	Image annotation	Several ten types of annotations for segmentation for object detection.	Typically, thousands of images are annotated for training.

	[GPE20] [LMB14]		
	Point cloud Map [HPW22] [SKD20] [KRW24]	Around several 10 points per m ² , for each frame, the frame rate around 10hz.	According to space size, from thousands of data samples to a hundred million.

4.2.1.1 Synthetic Data Generation for IoT applications

Simulation Approaches

Simulation approaches can be divided into two main categories: (i) *semantic model-based simulations* that emphasize high-level relationships between entities in smart environments using abstract models to simulate activities and interactions; and (ii) *physical model-based simulations* that focus on replicating real-world physical processes, generating detailed, modality-specific data such as sensory readings. In semantic model-based simulations, relationships and functions between entities are manually set and implemented. Physical model-based simulations, on the other hand, calculate interactions based on physical laws and mathematical formulas for high-precision outcomes.

In the device level of IoT systems, semantic model-based simulation methods are developed for many different data types. For example, tools like OpenSHS [ASC17], Persim-3d [LCL15], and IE Sim [SCN14] are developed to analyze and generate datasets of Activities of Daily Living (ADL) for smart home applications, including lighting, security, and energy management. Semantic models are used to represent the relationships of entities at the device level, network level and application level. They define functions for different interactions among the entities and thus, naturally synthesize different level data with the functions customized to specific relationships. On a larger scale, the Exploring [PY21] framework involves a task-based approach with the Digital Twin of a city where citizens are engaged in performing certain activities to create data that reflects hypothetical scenarios. A Digital Twin replicates real-world entities, in this case, a city. It integrates data from various sources to create a comprehensive model that can simulate and predict the physical existence of the city, including aspects like traffic flow, energy consumption, and environmental impact.

The semantic model is also a powerful tool to model relationships in network components. Network Simulator 3 (ns-3) [RH10] is a discrete-event network simulator that simulates the behavior of various network protocols and configurations, providing a highly flexible environment for testing and development. Semantic model enhances ns-3 by offering a structured framework for simulating nodes, links, protocols, and applications. This integration allows users to simulate realistic network traffic data and analyze the performance of network configurations.

Known for the robust capability to guide simulations on the device and network levels, semantic models extend their utility to higher-level simulations involving application knowledge. This capability is particularly useful in complex IoT systems where different levels of data are integrated. A leading example is SmartSPEC [CJG22], a simulation tool that synthesizes realistic occupancy and customizable sensor data across both device and network levels. It uses a four-component semantic model—Space, Event, Person, and Sensors—to capture intricate human activity patterns within a smart environment. SmartSPEC generates data based on Wi-Fi occupancy datasets and allows full customization of data generation functions. Its key feature is the ability to learn event distributions from seed data, enabling it to extract abstract information about events and activities, thus transforming raw data into application-level insights.

Physical model simulation involves creating detailed, often mathematical models of physical systems to understand and predict their behavior under various conditions. To synthesize sensor

data, physical-based methods create high-precision simulations of specific phenomena like acoustic signals (e.g., Soundspaces 2.0 [CSG22]) or point clouds (Lidarsim [MWW20]). These methods are based on well-defined physical scenarios, including the environment, and physical data of entities (3D model, surface texture and parameters, etc.) to simulate physical sensory data or network reflection data. Thus, these methods are used as a simulator from the device level to sensor data or even the network level, while the high-precision sensory data can be further utilized by other applications.

Robotic trajectory generation is another field that wildly uses mathematics equations to simulate the target object. One approach is the optimal rough terrain trajectory framework [HK07], which solves the optimal path for wheeled mobile robots navigating through uneven and rough terrains like the moon. The method performs physical simulation to solve realistic physical data of the position, velocity, and acceleration but doesn't account for obstacles or collisions. Trajectory Generation for Mobile Robots in Dynamic Environments [BHK21] using Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) combines long-range planning with dynamic obstacle avoidance and real-time adaptability. Both methods excel in their specific applications and their focus on individual sensor modalities to simulate and limit their integration into broader scenarios of IoT systems.

Machine Learning Approaches

Machine Learning approaches are useful to automatically generate synthetic data from existing data. These approaches, particularly built to deal with time-series data collected by sensors in IoT systems, involve traditional machine learning models and deep learning models. Traditional machine learning techniques like Synthetic Data with Nested Markov Chain [PAP23], combine synthetic data generation techniques with nested Markov chain to model complex dependencies. For example, in the context of smart lighting control, a nested Markov chain can model the probabilities of different lighting conditions and occupant behaviors over time to optimize energy efficiency.

Deep Learning models utilize multiple layers of neural networks to optimize a loss function to a target. These methods can be regarded as approximating functions from input to output with arbitrary precision with the sufficient large scale of the Neural Network. These models, particularly generative ones, play a significant role in tasks such as time series generation, prediction, and hybrid approaches that combine simulation and Deep Learning. One approach involves deep learning generative models that create synthetic data from random distributions. These models learn to map random distributions to the distribution of real-world data. Generative models have been pivotal in producing synthetic time series data, images, and even more complex forms of data.

Using deep learning to generate synthetic data can be understood within a hierarchical framework. At the base of this hierarchy is the physical world, IoT sensors capture various forms of data such as images, videos, and 3D models. These sensors serve as the starting point for generating data, which is then transmitted and processed by IoT networks. As the physical sensor data is collected and processed, applications can make predictions and decisions based on this information, thus forming the foundation of IoT systems. Physical data generation becomes a fundamental start of this hierarchy with raw sensory data. As we focus more closely on IoT sensor data, the generative method is also prevalently used for data augmentation. For example, Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) [ACB17] based data augmentation [LDQ21] strategy for sensor anomaly detection by generating synthetic anomalies. This can help overcome the limitations of small or imbalanced datasets. Wi-Fi See It All [LLY20] involves the use of GAN to enhance Wi-Fi imaging technology that leverages the penetration and reflection characteristics of wireless signals to perceive and image the environment.

Network data generation is another area where deep learning shows promise. Synthetic attack [KS23] proposed a framework for with GAN used as data augmentation. This approach reduces the dependency on real-world data and offers a more flexible and ethically convenient model-building process. Other models, like TimeVAE [DFW21] and TimeTransformer [LWL24], utilize the generative model to generate time series data, capturing trends and seasonality. Both methods can generate synthetic data, yet the precision and flexibility in different settings are still problems.

On the application layer, some method utilizing generative methods for privacy preservation is proposed for Federated Learning. GFL [CZL23] use GAN with differential privacy to generate data while preserving privacy during server communication. Social GANs (Zhang, Wu, Dong, & Liu, 2021), another method, can learn pedestrian walking patterns from images to generate realistic human trajectories. Combining simulation and machine learning is another emerging trend in synthetic data generation. These hybrid methods integrate simulation techniques with large language models and vision large models to generate richer, more contextually informed data. For example, RFGGen [CZ23] uses large models to generate physical scenes and then simulates radio frequency responses based on these synthetic scenes, marking a significant advancement in creating realistic and contextually informed synthetic data.

In Appex B, you can find a detailed comparison of related articles for synthetic data generation in tabular format, for both simulation and machine learning approaches.

4.2.1.2 *Synthetic data generation for vision-based applications*

Deep learning algorithms are inherently data-driven, necessitating substantial datasets for effective training and generalization. In industrial settings, where new objects with diverse features, appearance and geometric characteristics may frequently be introduced, there is an increasing demand for rapid adaptation of AI frameworks to accommodate these objects (e.g. pose estimation algorithms). A common approach to address this challenge is the generation and utilization of synthetic data, though the domain gap between real and synthetic images is not always easily bridged. Recent methods like TexPose [CMN23] can be used to efficiently bridge the real-synthetic gap by learning rich texture representations of the object from synthetic and a few real images. An alternative approach, as highlighted in recent research, involves the use of Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF)-based methods [TWZ23], which can generate realistic novel views of objects from a sparse subset of input images, thereby reducing the time and expertise required for data acquisition. Novel view synthesis is an actively pursued research topic in computer vision, which aims to synthesize novel views using a sparse set of input RGB images. However, this task is far from trivial and gives rise to many challenges, such as ensuring realistic underlying geometry of the objects in the scene, modeling realistic lighting conditions, and ensuring consistency of the novel views.

Early novel view synthesis approaches were based on light fields and image-based rendering techniques [GGS96], whereas the rise of Structure-from-Motion (SfM) [SSS06] revolutionized the field. SfM produces a sparse point cloud of the scene using an input collection of overlapping photos. Many advances (COLMAP [SF16], GLOMAP [Sa21], VGG-SfM [JKR23]) were made in this field that enabled the creation of accurate dense point clouds and detailed textured meshes, some of them as a result of very recent work. However, these methods struggled with accurately reconstructing fine geometry and handling complex lighting effects, especially with sparse input data. SfM relies on explicit, discrete representations like point clouds, meshes, and voxels, which require substantial storage. Synthetic image or video generation are proposed to alleviate input shortage. Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) [ACB17] that contains a generator and a discriminator work together is widely used to generate synthetic images and improve image quality iteratively. Similarly, Stable Diffusion [RBL22] uses convolutional neural networks for

compression and denoising models to produce high-quality images efficiently. Then for video generations, Grid-Diffusion [LKK24] presents a novel approach to generating videos from text descriptions by creating keyframes and interpolating between them. Other models such as Free-bloom [HFS24], combine Large Language Models (LLMs) with diffusion models to maintain consistency in video generation.

In contrast, newer approaches like NeRF offer continuous, implicit representations, capturing finer details and view-dependent effects, though at the cost of computational complexity and longer training times. Make-It-3D [TWZ23] can create high-fidelity 3D content from only a single image using prior knowledge from a 2D diffusion model as 3D-aware supervision for 3D creation. It follows a two-stage optimization: firstly, optimizing a NeRF with image constraints, then transforming the model into textured point clouds. NeRF is introduced in 2020 by Mildenhall et al. [MPH20], which represented a scene with a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) whose input was a single 5D vector comprised of the spatial location and the viewing direction, and whose output was the volume density and the view-dependent emitted radiance (color). They introduced harmonic embedding to enable MLPs to approximate higher frequency functions and stratified sampling to vastly reduce the computational overhead of the ray-marching algorithm, thus improving the quality of the view synthesis while reducing the training time. Since then, several key improvements have been made to the original NeRF implementation that addresses quality [BMP21], [ZRS10], speed [MHR22], [RPL21], [GKJ21], and few-shot view synthesis [YYT21], [YPW23]. Mip-NeRF enhanced the accuracy and speed by rendering anti-aliased conical frustums instead of rays and reducing aliasing artifacts. InstantNGP [MHR22] significantly boosted performance by exploiting a hash and an occupancy grid together with a smaller MLP. Barron et al. [BMV22] also proposed Mip-NeRF 360 (an extension of Mip-NeRF) that achieved extremely high-quality renderings by optimizing further the model. However, this comes with the cost of very large training times, making real-time high-resolution rendering not feasible.

Furthermore, methods like PlenOctrees [M22] that used an MLP to predict a spherical harmonic representation of radiance and Plenoxels [YLL22], which focused on optimizing a voxel representation of the scene. NeRF-based view synthesis requires neural networks that are computationally expensive both to train and render. Most advancements focus either on speed or quality, and they cannot achieve both at the same level. In 2023, 3D Gaussian Splatting for Real-Time Radiance Field Rendering [KM23] was introduced. Similar to Plenoxels, they do not use Neural Networks and exploit spherical harmonics to model complex lighting conditions. The key idea is the creation of 3D Gaussians initialized by an SfM-produced sparse point cloud, optimizing the parameters of the Gaussians (position, anisotropic covariance, alpha, SH coefficients), controlling the density of the Gaussians over the optimization (e.g., clone, split), and using a fast differentiable rendering approach for anisotropic splatting of the Gaussians. These concepts allow for real-time high-resolution rendering, producing similar quality views to NeRF but in much less time.

In industrial environments, a crucial aspect is the localization of objects and products, as well as the assessment of defects through visual means. This capability is essential for ensuring quality control and operational efficiency. Techniques like SplatPose & Detect [KRW24] enable pose-agnostic anomaly detection by leveraging 3D representations through 3D Gaussian splatting (3DGS). The models are trained to learn the distribution of defect-free instances, allowing them to effectively identify anomalies during inference.

Conclusions

This section presents existing synthetic data generation techniques for both IoT (time-series) and vision datasets. Initially, we categorized different types of data that can be generated in the application, network and device layers. At the application layer data related to the application domain are generated (e.g., failure types), at the network layer data related to the networking

infrastructure can be generated (e.g., latency, bandwidth, etc.) and finally, at the device layer data related to the device observations are generated (e.g., images of a camera). Existing techniques can be based on simulations or Machine Learning approaches. A summary of important research gaps is provided in Section 4.2.6, aiming to define the innovative PANDORA technique for synthetic data generation.

4.2.2 AI-Driven Modeling and Development for Uncertainty Quantification

Understanding and controlling uncertainty is critical in current machine learning, particularly for high-stakes applications [GTA23]. Uncertainty in machine learning can develop because of variability in data, model assumptions, or external variables, making uncertainty measurement a key task. There are two sorts of uncertainty: aleatoric (data's intrinsic randomness) and epistemic (a lack of knowledge that can be reduced with additional data or better models). More recently, credal uncertainty, which reflects uncertainty about the probability model itself, has gained popularity.

This review will look at key approaches and theoretical frameworks for modeling aleatoric, epistemic, and credal uncertainty in machine learning, with a focus on their application to deep learning. It will assess existing uncertainty quantification approaches, identify emerging trends, and explore current issues and future research prospects.

First, an overview of the theoretical foundations of uncertainty in machine learning will be discussed. Then, a review of key methods for managing uncertainty. Finally, a summary of ongoing debates, emerging areas, and future research directions.

4.2.2.1 *Theoretical foundations of uncertainty in machine learning*

The difference between aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty is implanted in probability theory. Aleatoric arises from inherent noise or randomness in the data, rendering it irreducible. Whereas epistemic uncertainty is caused by a lack of understanding and can be reduced with more data. As machine learning models progressed, the difficulty of quantifying uncertainty became increasingly apparent, particularly with the rise of neural networks.

The application of Bayesian approaches in deep learning laid the groundwork for dealing with epistemic uncertainty in neural networks [KG17]. Bayesian approaches, such as Bayesian Neural Networks (BNNs) and Gaussian Processes (GPs), are crucial for measuring epistemic uncertainty through the posterior distributions that can be updated when new data becomes available. Then, the credal sets were recently developed as a framework for managing credal uncertainty, which is uncertainty regarding the model itself. The concept of credal sets and classifiers provide more robust approaches to deal with credal uncertainty [HW21], particularly in high-stakes situations. These credal sets provide a framework for representing a various range of probability distributions, which enables more robust decision-making in confusing situations.

4.2.2.2 *Review of Key Methods*

Deterministic approaches are based on a network with fixed parameters and where each forward pass yields the same output. These techniques split into two categories: quantification of internal and external uncertainty. Internal methods strive to represent model uncertainty and improve predictions on in-distribution versus out-of-distribution samples [SKK18] & [MG18]. External methods [RBS19] evaluate uncertainty using different networks in order to eliminate bias from the primary prediction job. These deterministic approaches have the advantage of being computationally efficient and applicable to pre-trained networks. However, their reliance on a single architecture and sensitivity to training data may result in predictions that are overly confident or unrealistic optimistic.

Bayesian Neural Networks (BNNs) handle both types of uncertainty by considering network weights as distributions [BCK15], which effectively captures epistemic uncertainty. Because accurate Bayesian inference is computationally expensive, approximations such as Monte Carlo dropout and variational inference are utilized instead. BNNs provide robust estimates for both aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty by modeling parameter distributions rather than fixed values, resulting in more reliable predictions, particularly in noisy or data-limited contexts. However, their shortcomings include computational complexity, as training BNNs frequently necessitates advanced inference techniques.

Ensemble Methods: combine the predictions from several models instead of a single model. This aims to improve accuracy and robustness. Through these approaches, the measurement of the uncertainty is enhanced [LPB17]. Indeed, the aleatoric uncertainty is measured by the consensus across predictions. In contrast, the variety of models is reflected in epistemic uncertainty. Better prediction performance and reliable uncertainty measures are the results of this. However, these approaches are computationally expensive for training and inference as they use several models.

Test-Time Data Augmentation: During inference, the input data is augmented to generate several predictions from a single model. This approach measures the aleatoric uncertainty as it reflects variations in the input data itself. The key benefits include better robustness and more confidence in output predictions because it allows the model to analyze a diverse range of input possibilities. However, this strategy is constrained by its reliance on the precise sorts of augmentations used, which may fail to reflect the underlying uncertainty in more complex data distributions.

Credal Networks: a robust framework for capturing both aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty, credal networks are a recent development in uncertainty quantification [HSH24]. Instead of producing a single posterior distribution, these networks use sets of probability distributions (credal sets). These sets provide a more trustworthy representation of uncertainty. Although credal networks demand a lot of computational resources, they are more resilient to Out-of-Distribution (OOD) data and missing data. In scenarios characterized by high levels of epistemic uncertainty, credal classifiers are especially beneficial as they provide more conservative predictions. In addition, while epistemic uncertainty can be effectively handled by probabilistic models, aleatoric uncertainty calls for more advanced techniques like ensemble and Bayesian approaches. Credal classifiers provide more cautious uncertainty estimates.

4.2.2.3 *Ongoing Debates and Emerging Areas*

Debates: A main topic surrounding uncertainty quantification is on how to quantify and apply epistemic and aleatoric uncertainty in machine learning, particularly in situations involving crucial decisions [GOS23]. In addition to improving machine learning algorithms' performance, robustness and accuracy [KG17], being able to distinguish between aleatoric and epistemic uncertainties is crucial for decision-making processes that require human judgment.

In active learning contexts, where choosing the most informative cases for labeling can result in significant increases in model performance, an understanding of epistemic uncertainty is very helpful. In fact, the learning process can be greatly enhanced by a targeted approach to uncertainty measurement as opposed to a broad measure.

New Frontiers: Uncertainty quantification gained more interest recently especially in unsupervised and reinforcement learning contexts [GTA23]. Credal sets are being applied in dynamic environments, such as autonomous systems, where effectively representing uncertainty across various models is crucial. Hybrid models that integrate probabilistic and credal methods may offer a balanced solution, providing a compromise between computational efficiency and accuracy.

Merging the different uncertainties for active learning: By merging epistemic and aleatoric uncertainty, we get a more complete picture of the model's performance. By analyzing them together, we can distinguish between areas where new data can enhance the model (epistemic uncertainty) and those where further progress is limited due to inherent noise (aleatoric uncertainty). Furthermore, credal sets broaden the concept of uncertainty by reflecting a collection of plausible models rather than just one. Credal uncertainty blends epistemic and aleatoric uncertainties, providing a more nuanced view of prediction dependability and aiding in the refinement of uncertainty sampling tactics [NVS22].

When these tactics are paired with active learning, the strategy becomes extremely effective. The goal is to drive data gathering or annotation efforts by focusing on regions of high epistemic uncertainty, which can be identified using Bayesian approaches, ensembling, or credal sets. Active learning process can prioritize selecting some examples depending on the epistemic or credal uncertainty, resulting in the most informative labels. This will help guarantee that new data is collected where it can have the biggest influence on reducing epistemic uncertainty. Simultaneously considering the constraints given by aleatoric uncertainty. So, an active learning technique that includes the examination of epistemic, aleatoric, and credal uncertainty allows for more targeted, efficient, and trustworthy model training.

4.2.2.4 Conclusion

While probabilistic methods are effective in managing aleatoric uncertainty, current developments in credal networks and Bayesian methods show promise in managing epistemic and credal uncertainty. These techniques are especially useful in high-stakes scenarios when the reliability of the model is crucial.

In high-dimensional, sparse-data contexts, there are still a lot of unanswered questions, especially in the areas of unsupervised learning and reinforcement learning. Furthermore, in order to manage credal uncertainty in real-time systems without incurring undue computational costs, more computationally efficient approaches are required [GTA23].

The development of hybrid models combining epistemic, credal, and aleatoric uncertainty with an active learning process should be the main goal of future study.

4.2.3 Explainable AI Through Domain Knowledge

The integration of domain knowledge is a key point in the development of explainable AI models. By leveraging ontologies, knowledge bases, rules, and physics laws, domain knowledge can not only improve the accuracy of the inference process in specific contexts but also guide the discovery of explanations. Symmetry has a central importance in this line of research, since it allows for a relevant reduction of the number of parameters in explainable AI models. Tools such as GENEOS for applications in TDA and ML [BFG19], [CFQ22], [FFQ23], [BBB23], along with new theoretical methods incorporating GENEOS into networks, can be utilized for explainable AI. The use of GENEOS is motivated by their topological and geometric properties, based on a precise mathematical theory, by their interaction with the theory of action of transformation groups, and by their modularity, which allows them to be composed to form more complex GENEOS. Additionally, discovering stationary data meta-features can help generate Shapley-like explanations, while analyzing data subspaces, combined with background knowledge, can support surrogate model and attention-based explanations. These methods allow us not only to create innovative, domain-specific explainable models but also identify data quality issues that need to be addressed during the data cleaning process. The advantages of these models can be demonstrated through comparative evaluations with non-domain-informed models.

The “Explainable AI Through Domain Knowledge” aims at the following goals:

- Strong reduction of the dimensionality of the problems.
- Use of interpretable or (at least) explainable operators.
- Development of a new mathematical approach to explainability in AI.
- Development of new causal explainability methods, incorporating both observational data and environmental knowledge to improve explanation accuracy.

4.2.3.1 *Enhancing Learning Explainability by Leveraging Geometrical Symmetries Through GENEOS*

Group Equivariant Non-Expansive Operators can be used to reduce the dimensionality of the data, using the symmetries associated with the problem considered. To this end, small libraries of operators sensitive to the presence of appropriate data patterns can be created and convex combinations of these operators can be used to build more complex GENEOS, suitable for analyzing the available information in an explainable way, exploiting the intrinsic interpretability of the GENEOS used. A precise mathematical concept of explainability associated with the approximation of operators through small GENEOS networks can also be developed and applied.

4.2.3.2 *Incorporating Domain Knowledge into Causal Explanations for Observational Data*

Causal discovery has received considerable attention in recent decades to identify causal relationships among random variables only from observational data hence overcoming economic or ethical concerns of interventions or randomized controlled trials. Most approaches to causal discovery assume that no prior knowledge about the underlying causal graph is available, meaning that all causal relationships are equally plausible a priori [C03], [YM13]. In practice, however, domain experts often have information about the causal relationships between subsets of variables. They may know from prior experimentation and/or domain expertise that, e.g., two variables directly causally influence each other, certain pairs of variables cannot be causally connected, or that there is a causal hierarchy of variables. It may then be beneficial to integrate this domain knowledge into the causal discovery procedure to improve both computational efficiency and accuracy by reducing the search space of graphs in causal discovery [Z08].

This subcomponent aims to incorporate domain knowledge into the explanation derivation process, including rules and constraints that can refine and support causal analysis. What form exactly expert knowledge takes in practice is still an open question, from simple edge knowledge, to knowing the existence of a "causal path" and to modeling expert belief. On the one hand, it will examine different levels of abstraction depending on the target users (e.g., end users, system designers). On the other hand, it will propose different types of explanations based on the scenario, such as counterfactual and contrastive explanations that facilitate what-if analysis. Explainability techniques such as, among others, Shapley values and integrated gradients will be used. The use of these techniques will enable us to interpret the contributions of individual features in the studied use cases. This will allow us to provide domain-specific explainable models and to identify data quality issues that need to be addressed during the data cleaning process. The PANDORA project will benefit from the use of these methods both to identify the features that characterize the production of realistic data for neural network training and to incorporate domain knowledge into deep networks during the construction and training phases.

4.2.3.3 *Key methods*

- **Group Equivariant Non-Expansive Operators (GENEOS):** GENEOS are functional operators that simplify data while preserving their symmetries. They are used to

approximate real observers and their actions on the data. Their use benefits from a pre-existing and well-grounded geometric theory.

- **Shapley values:** Shapley values measure the total gains of game players, assuming full collaboration. They represent 'fair' distributions in the sense that they are the only distributions satisfying certain desirable properties. Additionally, they can be used to quantify the contribution of each agent in achieving a collective goal.
- **Integrated gradients (IG):** IG is an interpretability technique applicable to any differentiable model (e.g., images, text, structured data). It offers computational efficiency and strong theoretical properties.
- **Time Series Variable Selection (TSVS):** [CGK23], [VLC24] is a scalable Time-Series Variables Selection algorithm that selects all the minimal-size subsets of TS whose past leads to an optimal predictive model for the future (forecasting) of a given target variable. Identifying all solutions to the variable selection problem leads to gaining insights, domain intuition, and a better understanding of the data-generating mechanism; it is often the first step in causal modeling.

4.2.3.4 Conclusion

The availability of new geometric, topological, and statistical techniques promises to make a new approach to explainable artificial intelligence feasible. On the one hand, recent theoretical advancements have made new operators for explainable artificial intelligence available, along with new procedures to compose them into small networks with a limited number of parameters. On the other hand, the development of new algorithms for the selection of all possible pertinent combinations of time-series variables will for a better understanding of the data generation process and the causal modeling of the phenomena related to them. These innovations promise to be useful in this component of the project.

4.2.4 Automated Annotation, Labeling, and Completion of Data

4.2.4.1 Data completion

Data completeness is one of the most important dataset quality attributes, especially in machine learning, since many SOTA machine learning algorithms are designed for datasets without missing values [GLX23]. For such ML algorithms an appropriate missing value inference (MVI) or data imputation algorithm has to be applied prior to model training. A large number of MVI methods have been proposed in the literature. For a particular dataset containing missing values, a MVI method should be selected considering its data types, missing rates and post-imputation prediction task [MWC22].

A recent article by Zhou et al. (2024) [ZAB24] gives an overview of SOTA MVI methods that can be grouped into the following four categories: statistical-based methods, ML-based methods, MVI methods based on deep learning algorithms and MVI methods based on optimization algorithms. Besides those broad four categories, the authors also emphasize that in practice MVI is often handled by simply deleting data points with missing values.

Statistical-based MVI can be further divided into two sub-categories: single imputation methods and multiple imputation methods. Single imputation methods are simple algorithms (usually used as baselines) that replace a missing value with a single estimated value. Well known and widely used single imputation algorithms are mean, median and mode imputation calculating the mean, median or mode of non-missing values per feature and using these averages to impute missing

values. There are also single imputation methods specifically designed for time-series (e.g., LOCF – last observation carried forward, and NOCB – next observation carried backward). Multiple imputation involves replacing a missing value with more than one possible value resulting in multiple completed datasets that are then analyzed and combined to obtain final missing value estimates. Typical multiple imputation approaches are: maximum likelihood imputation, matrix completion methods (usually based on principal component analysis and matrix factorization) and Bayesian approaches (e.g., MICE – multivariate imputation by chained equation, and MCMC – Markov Chain Monte Carlo)

Machine learning methods for MVI rely on supervised learning algorithms to determine missing values in datasets, leveraging available non-missing data for more precise estimates than simple statistics [IZI24]. Those methods train either a regression model (in the case of numerical datasets) or a classification model (in the case of categorical datasets), typically regression models are chosen after performing one-hot encoding transformation for categorical features. Widely used regression models for MVI are linear, lasso, ridge and elastic net regression, but also regression based on adapted classification algorithms – support vector machines, k-nearest neighbors and random forest.

Deep learning MVI involves training a deep neural network. Besides classical feed-forward neural networks, DL-based MVI methods also use variational autoencoders, generative adversarial networks and diffusion-based generative neural network architectures. Although DL-based methods are generally considered superior to ML-based MVI methods, empirical analysis conducted by Sun et al. (2023) [SLX23] indicates that ML-based techniques usually perform better on smaller datasets containing less than 30000 data points. Finally, optimization-based methods can be exploited to fine-tune any of the previously mentioned MVI methods (e.g., genetic algorithms).

It is also important to emphasize that MVI methods can be adapted for synthetic data generation. For example, Neves et al. (2022) [NAN22] proposed tabulator, a meta-method for synthetic data generation that uses MVI methods based on generative adversarial networks.

4.2.4.2 *Data annotation and labeling*

Supervised/semi-supervised machine learning techniques require completely/partially annotated datasets such that contained data points are labeled with concepts or categories which the corresponding machine model has to learn. Annotating a large amount of data points is a labor-intensive, cognitive-intensive and financially costly process [WBM23]. This is one of the main reasons why researchers have started developing (semi-)automated methods that reduce human effort and data annotation costs.

Organizing the labeling experience as human-machine collaboration has the potential to improve labeling quality and reduce human effort. Desmond et al. (2021) [DDB21] studied AI assistance in labeling and semi-automated labeling. In a semi-automated labeling paradigm the predictive model (the machine labeler) not only assists the human when deciding on which labels to apply, but is also capable of automating some portion of the labeling task itself. In the semi-automatic paradigm this process continues until the human is satisfied with the labeling performance of the machine labeler and delegates labeling of the remaining data without further intervention.

Data annotation is a machine learning task that involves converting unprocessed primary data such as images, voice, text, and video into machine recognizable information. The quality of labeling has a great impact on performance of learning models [YGY23]. As emphasized by Zhang et al. (2021) [ZJN21], the quality of image annotation depends on the accuracy of the bounding box marked around the object. For voice annotation, it is highly important to ensure that voice time-series are synchronized with the corresponding phonetic symbols. Different quality standards can be applied for different text annotation tasks. In the data annotation stage,

evaluation metrics should reflect three aspects: image, audio, and text, including labeling accuracy, word error rate, sentence error rate, character error rate, word segmentation without ambiguity, sentiment rating category accuracy, semantic accuracy, and text data fluency [ZJN21].

Transfer learning is an efficient approach that can reasonably reduce the negative impact of limited data. Still, annotating data is a resource consuming task for a real-world implementation with no pre-labeled dataset. Labeled datasets help to train machine learning models to identify and understand the recurring patterns in the input for delivering accurate output [ZJN21].

Another novel approach in data labeling is using active learning which allows a learning algorithm to actively query a user to label data with the desired outputs. Active learning can reduce the amount of manual labor required by prioritizing the most informative data sample for labeling. Recent progress in active learning has shown promising results in speeding up human-in-the-loop annotation. Using GPT-4, Pangakis et al. (2023) [PWF23] validate approach of using generative large language models (LLMs) to augment text annotation procedures by replicating 27 annotation tasks across 11 datasets from recent social science articles in high-impact journals. This showed that LLM performance for text annotation is promising but highly contingent on both the dataset and the type of annotation task, which reinforces the necessity to validate on a task-by-task basis. To help models learn with fewer labels, both self-supervised learning and semi-supervised learning has shown substantial progress, achieving competitive results against supervised baselines with limited supervisions. In summary, leveraging the latest advances in self-supervised learning, authors developed a nearest neighbor graph-based approach that can perform versatile downstream tasks and quickly incorporate new information in a semi-supervised manner, suitable for integration with real time human-in-the-loop systems.

4.2.4.3 Data augmentation

The quality and quantity of training machine learning models is affected by quality and quantity of training data. Models trained with limited data suffer from over-fitting with significantly degenerative performance on testing datasets, and models trained with unbalanced samples will lead to poor generalization ability. Simple solution for this problem is acquiring more data, but in many cases data is hard to source and labeling new sets of instances can be labor-intensive work. To solve this problem, data augmentation has been extensively applied and proven to be effective and efficient [WWL24]. In general, data augmentation is accomplished by either transforming training samples in some desired manner for use as additional training data or by creating completely new samples from scratch. Transformation operations can be applied directly on input data or indirectly by manipulating feature vectors in intermediate layers of deep neural networks [MM22]. Augmentation approaches can be divided into the following category of methods: (1) *individual* methods which transforms one data sample without referring to others to create new data, (2) *multiple* methods make use of multiple data to acquire new ones, and (3) *population* augmentation methods that do not explicitly make use of one or multiple data but rather uses the population of the data. Depending on the type of data different augmentation approaches are used [WWL24].

Data augmentation for image data revolves around the manipulation of the colors and spatial relationships of image pixels. For individual augmentation some of the most popular transformations include pixel erasing, photometric and geometric transformations, image cropping, and automatic augmentation. Image mixup, neural blending and image patching are the most popular multiple image augmentation methods. Finally, generative adversarial networks, neural style transfer and computer graphics modeling are some of mostly used populational image augmentation approaches.

With the rise of LLMs there are more possibilities for text data augmentation. Individual augmentation methods are mostly used, and they include invarian replacement, token addition,

token deletion, sentence cropping, sentence morphing, back-translation and hierarchical augmentation. For multiple text augmentation, most used methods are text mixup and text fragment merging. Population text augmentation includes traditional models and LLMs.

Graph data augmentation includes augmentation of values stored in graph structure as well as topology of structure. Individual graph augmentation includes node attribute augmentation, naive topology perturbation, subgraphing, graph diffusion, graph rewiring, and graph structure learning. Multiple graph augmentation relies on methods like propagation and graph mixup, and population graph augmentation is based on diffusion models.

Tabular data is a much more simple way of storing data compared with other modalities. In tabular data augmentation switching the sequence of rows and columns in most cases does not affect information stored by the table. This is the reason why most tabular data augmentation methods leverage the value information. As individual tabular augmentations mostly used are value-based transformations such as table masking, feature engineering, but structure-based transformation table subsetting can be used as well. Multiple tabular augmentation methods include tabular mixup and structural relaxation. Widely used tabular augmentation methods fit into the population tabular augmentation category and include autoencoders and generative adversarial networks (GAN). Autoencoder approach uses four types of autoencoders that all generate data sets which produce better task performance, while one variant called variational autoencoder provides the most robust result. GAN mainly considers the privacy issue, and experiments show that the augmented table given by GAN is compatible with downstream machine learning models. Another population tabular augmentation method is relational structure construction which learns the relational structure and corresponding functional relationships from tabular datasets and uses this basis to generate new samples.

Data augmentation methods for time-series data either focus on manipulating the value at each timestamp or manipulating the sequence of timestamps. Individual time-series augmentation methods are value perturbation, decomposition, window sliding, and sequence morphing. The most commonly used multiple time-series augmentation method is sequence mixing, and mostly used population augmentation methods are GAN and statistical generation. Although the GAN frameworks have received significant attention in many fields, how to generate effective time series data still remains a challenging problem [WSY21]. Most recently, variational autoencoders (VAEs) based data augmentation of time-series are investigated for human activity recognition.

In most cases, simple and standard augmentation schemes give competitive results and can be effectively used as a viable alternative to the more complex ones. It is common to first apply more basic augmentations before employing the advanced methods to further augment data beyond what can reasonably be achieved by these basic techniques [MM22].

Conclusions

Our literature review of the state-of-the-art methods for data completion, labeling and augmentation indicates that there are many different methods based on different machine learning approaches for missing value inference, missing label inference, and generation of artificial data points like real ones. However, for a single dataset, data imputation models inferring missing values of distinct features are usually independently trained. Thus, our research focus will be to exploit various transfer learning strategies when training such models. In the case of neural networks, transfer learning can be achieved by reusing different parts of the network in terms of neural network weights and biases. This means that when training a neural network-based data imputation model for a feature, we can reuse parts of previously trained data imputation models for features from the same dataset. To account for heterogeneity and bias in data domain dependent adaptations could be also applied. By training decision-tree based surrogate models for neural network-based data imputation models, missing value inference rules

can be derived, validated, and expanded by domain experts in order to achieve explainable missing value inference.

Data labeling or missing label inference is a special case of missing value inference for a class attribute determining data categories. In this regard, all previously described novel approaches can be adapted for graph learning algorithms and graph-based models inferring missing labels. Data augmentation methods are usually data specific techniques. In the PANDORA project, we will develop novel oversampling techniques generalizable to different data types (tabular data, timeseries, images) that consider local intrinsic dimensionality and hubness properties of data spaces that are abstracted via appropriate graph representations (e.g., kNN graphs). A very important aspect of missing value/label inference and data augmentation models is their quality control. Commonly this involves human supervision, but in the PANDORA project this issue will be addressed by validating inference results relying on hybrid unsupervised anomaly detection models combining representational learning and clustering.

4.2.5 Techniques for Data Summarization, Dimensionality Reduction, and Fusion

Introduction

Dimensionality reduction and feature extraction are crucial steps in data analysis, addressing the challenges posed by large, complex datasets. As the dimensionality of data increases, the risk of overfitting, noise, and computational inefficiencies becomes more pronounced. By reducing the number of features or dimensions, we can simplify data representation, retain meaningful patterns, and improve the performance of subsequent models. Whether used in exploratory data analysis or in machine learning pipelines, these techniques are fundamental for uncovering hidden structures, enhancing interpretability, and ensuring that models generalize well to new data [RRL20], [JWS22].

Dimensionality reduction simplifies datasets by reducing the number of variables while preserving important information. Feature extraction, on the other hand, transforms raw data into a new set of features that encapsulate the essence of the original variables. Both approaches work toward the goal of improving computational efficiency and revealing patterns that might be obscured by redundant or irrelevant information.

Key Methods for Dimensionality Reduction and Feature Extraction

One of the most widely used techniques is *Principal Component Analysis (PCA)*, a linear method that identifies new orthogonal axes, or principal components, that capture the maximum variance in the data [JJM18]. By projecting the data onto these principal components, PCA reduces dimensionality while preserving the most significant patterns. It has proven effective across domains like pattern recognition, finance, and image processing, where simplifying data without losing valuable information is crucial. PCA also supports incremental versions, making it efficient in handling streaming or real-time data, as it continually adjusts the principal components as new data arrives.

Similar to PCA, *Singular Value Decomposition (SVD)* decomposes data matrices into singular vectors and singular values, allowing for dimensionality reduction by focusing on the most significant singular components. SVD is particularly valuable in fields like image compression and large-scale data analysis, where it efficiently captures the most meaningful patterns without overwhelming computational resources. Its ability to reduce the rank of large matrices by discarding smaller singular values helps simplify datasets while maintaining critical structures.

Another method frequently employed for dimensionality reduction is *Independent Component Analysis (ICA)*. While PCA focuses on variance, ICA aims to extract independent sources from mixed signals by maximizing statistical independence. This makes ICA particularly useful in fields such as biomedical signal processing, where separating signals (like EEG data) into independent

components is essential. ICA offers a more refined approach when there is an assumption that the underlying signals are statistically independent, enabling more accurate data representations and reducing dimensional complexity.

While PCA, ICA, and SVD are effective linear techniques, non-linear methods are invaluable for uncovering complex, intricate relationships in high-dimensional datasets. *t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE)* is one such method that excels at capturing non-linear patterns and relationships, making it highly effective for visualizing and exploring high-dimensional data. t-SNE projects data into a lower-dimensional space by preserving local relationships between data points, which often reveals hidden clusters or meaningful patterns that might be missed by linear methods. t-SNE's strength lies in its ability to maintain neighborhood relationships, making it particularly suitable for exploratory analysis in fields like genomics and image recognition [AFS21].

A key approach to dimensionality reduction focuses on *feature importance* [LJC17] a concept that assesses the contribution of individual features to the performance of a predictive model. This can be especially useful in machine learning applications, where selecting the most important features can significantly reduce the complexity of the model without sacrificing accuracy. Ensemble methods like Random Forests or Gradient Boosting Machines (GBMs) are commonly used to determine feature importance. These models evaluate how much each feature contributes to reducing prediction error by computing importance scores. Features with higher importance scores contribute more to the model's decision-making process, allowing analysts to retain only the most relevant features. This method not only simplifies the dataset but also enhances the interpretability and performance of machine learning models by eliminating irrelevant or redundant variables.

In addition to ensemble-based approaches, *correlation analysis* offers another pathway for reducing dimensionality. By examining the correlation matrix, highly correlated features can be identified and reduced to eliminate redundancy. When features are strongly correlated, they provide overlapping information, which can inflate the dimensionality of the dataset unnecessarily. By removing one feature from highly correlated pairs, analysts can reduce the dimensionality without losing meaningful information. This technique is especially useful during preprocessing steps, ensuring models are built using independent and informative features.

Autoencoders, a type of neural network, offer yet another approach to feature extraction and dimensionality reduction [GB18]. These models learn efficient representations of data by compressing it into a lower-dimensional latent space, retaining only the most critical features for reconstructing the original data. Autoencoders are particularly powerful for reducing dimensionality in high-dimensional data, such as images [HZZ21] or video frames.

Moving from feature-based methods to dynamic and temporal analyses, techniques like *Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD)* play a significant role in analyzing systems where time evolution is important. DMD identifies dominant patterns or "modes" that evolve over time, reducing the data to a set of significant dynamic modes. This is particularly useful in fields like fluid dynamics, robotics, or financial markets, where the data has inherent temporal structures. DMD helps reduce dimensionality while preserving the most critical time-dependent behaviors of the system [XWY23].

Lastly, *clustering methods*, although traditionally used for grouping data, can also indirectly serve as dimensionality reduction techniques [AMF21]. After clustering, each data point can be represented by its cluster membership or by using the cluster centroids, effectively reducing the number of features. This approach simplifies the data while preserving essential relationships between groups of similar data points. Clustering-based dimensionality reduction is often applied in market segmentation, customer behavior analysis, or even anomaly detection in large datasets.

Conclusions

While autoencoders have demonstrated strong performance in compressing high-dimensional data, their black-box nature often limits interpretability, which is crucial in fields like healthcare or finance where understanding the model's decision-making process is essential. Developing more interpretable feature extraction methods that provide transparency in how features are transformed and selected remains an important area of future research.

In conclusion, while significant advancements have been made in dimensionality reduction and feature extraction, there is a clear need for more adaptive, scalable, and interpretable methods. Addressing these gaps will not only improve model performance in high-dimensional, dynamic environments but also expand the applicability of these techniques to new and emerging fields, particularly those requiring real-time analysis and decision-making.

4.2.6 Research Gaps

There are several critical research gaps that need to be addressed to advance the field. First, in the area of synthetic data generation, there's a need for techniques that can produce trustworthy and realistic datasets tailored to specific environments or layers. This includes overcoming current limitations in IoT sensor data generation, such as lack of realism, causality violations, and issues with semantic explainability. Additionally, developing methods to create customizable and trustworthy IoT datasets using domain knowledge and scenario learning components is crucial.

Aside the domain gap between synthetic and real data with respect to the visual appearance, material properties along with unpredictable noise and imperfections that lead to a gap in generalization, the diversity of possible defects that occur in real-world scenarios that are challenging to simulate in the full extend and the complexity of subtle defects that affect the model sensitivity contribute to the above.

In the realm of uncertainty management, we need better methods to handle both epistemic and credal uncertainty, especially in high-stakes scenarios where errors can have significant consequences. Developing hybrid models that integrate various types of uncertainty with active learning techniques is another open challenge.

When it comes to data contexts and computational efficiency, there are unresolved issues in high-dimensional, sparse-data environments, particularly within unsupervised learning frameworks. More efficient strategies are needed to manage credal uncertainty in real-time systems to enhance their performance and reliability.

Explainable AI also presents a gap, with a need to apply new geometric, topological, and statistical techniques to practical problems. For data completion, labeling, and augmentation, enhancing data imputation models through transfer learning within neural networks, adapting data labeling methods to graph-based algorithms, and developing versatile oversampling techniques using graph representations like k-nearest neighbors (kNN) graphs are essential areas for further research.

Quality control and validation require the implementation of hybrid unsupervised anomaly detection methods that combine representational learning and clustering for automatic validation of inferred results. Federated Learning (FL) needs quality models for scenarios where centralizing the learning process is impractical due to security, privacy, or computational complexity. Developing FL models that can match or surpass the performance of centralized models in certain scenarios is also necessary.

Representational Learning (RL) calls for robust models that can generalize knowledge across diverse inference tasks, similar to multi-task learning, and applying representational learning in federated settings to enhance model robustness. Federated Representational Learning (FRL)

involves using attention-based FRL models, particularly for outlier detection, and developing new aggregation functions suitable for these models.

Efficiency and scalability are critical, with a need for methods that balance computational efficiency while capturing both linear and non-linear patterns, and techniques suitable for real-time and continuous data environments. Adaptability and assumptions require developing methods that do not rely on predefined assumptions and can adapt dynamically, as well as hybrid approaches that combine linear and non-linear methods for better performance.

In terms of interpretability, there is a need for more transparent autoencoders to create interpretable feature extraction methods, especially in critical fields like healthcare and finance. For dynamic and temporal data, combining Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) with other techniques to handle temporal data and applying these integrated methods to dynamic systems like robotics and autonomous vehicles is essential. Finally, advanced clustering techniques integrated with dimensionality reduction need to be researched, particularly for complex scenarios such as overlapping or hierarchical clusters.

Finally, in the realm of feature extraction, methods that focus on feature importance, such as Random Forests or Gradient Boosting Machines, are effective for selecting relevant features but are limited by the assumption that the most important features remain stable over time. In environments where data distributions change, such as in non-stationary settings, a more flexible approach to feature selection is required. This raises the need for adaptive feature selection mechanisms that can adjust to shifting data distributions in real-time without sacrificing model accuracy or interpretability

4.3 State-of-The-Art approaches for AIoT deployment and runtime operation

4.3.1 Resilient Learning Strategies for Sustained Intelligence

In the data-centric AI era, collecting data and improving its quality is of critical importance for predictive models based on machine/deep learning techniques. Even after collecting a large amount of data and applying appropriate data cleaning procedures (e.g., removing data instances that do not satisfy domain constraints, removing conflicting data instances and duplicates), data quality may still be an issue during model training [WSR23]. As indicated by Whang et al. (2023) [WSR23], flaws in training datasets can be categorized depending on whether data values are noisy or missing and depending on whether those flaws exist in data features or labels into the following four categories: (1) noisy features, (2) noisy labels, (3) missing feature values and (4) missing label values.

Resilient machine learning deals with the first, second and fourth type of training data flaws, whereas data imputation algorithms (also known as missing value inference algorithms) deal with missing feature values. More specifically, machine learning algorithms should be designed to be resilient to out-of-distribution data instances, i.e. data instances that cause a sharp drop in generalization capability of machine learning algorithms under distributional shifts. Such instances are either anomalies (data instances having noisy features and/or labels) or unlabelled data instances that belong to previously unseen or unknown classes or categories. In the first case, model training should be accompanied by an outlier/anomaly detection model, while in the second case the detection of unknown classes could be handled by open-world machine learning algorithms.

Anomalies or outliers are data instances in a sample that considerably deviate from other members of the sample or from some concept of normality [RKV21; NTN21; PSC21]. The detection of anomalies is widely used in a broad variety of applications and they can be classified into three categories: point anomalies, contextual anomalies and collective anomalies. A point

anomaly is an individual anomalous data instance (e.g., an illegal transaction, an image of damaged product in manufacturing). A contextual anomaly is a data instance that is anomalous in a specific time, space or structural context (e.g., time-series, spatial, spatio-temporal or graph-based anomalies). A collective anomaly is a set of related, consequent or dependent data instances that is contextually anomalous. A fundamental assumption in anomaly detection is that the data space region where the normal data instances exist can be bounded.

Depending on the presence of labels distinguishing normal data instances from anomalous ones, anomaly detection models can be either unsupervised (no labels indicating anomalies), semi-supervised (labels indicating anomalies are partially given, i.e. some anomalous data instances are labeled and some are not) or supervised (labels indicating anomalies are fully given) [NTN21]. Ruff et al. (2021) [RKV21] emphasizes that there are two big classes of anomaly detection algorithms, shallow and deep anomaly detection algorithms, that can be viewed from a unified perspective, depending on the type of anomaly detection model that belong to one of the following three categories: (1) density estimation and probabilistic models, (2) one-class classification models and (3) reconstruction models. Density estimation and probabilistic models predict anomalies through estimation of normal data probability distributions. Those methods include classical density estimation (e.g., the Mahalanobis distance, local outlier factor), energy-based models (e.g, deep belief networks, deep Boltzman machines) and neural generative models (e.g., variational autoencoders, generative adversarial networks). One-class classification is a discriminative approach to anomaly detection with the goal to learn a decision boundary separating normal from outlier data instances. Typical methods belonging to this category are one-class support vector machines, one-class neural networks and different variants of support vector data description. Finally, reconstruction models are based on learning low-dimensional data representations of normal data instances (e.g., different variants of principal component analysis, prototypical clustering and autoencoders).

The article by Pang et al. (2020) [PSC21] indicates main challenges and major issues in contemporary anomaly detection: low anomaly detection recall rate, anomaly detection in high-dimensional data, data-efficient learning of normality, noise-resilient anomaly detection, detection of complex anomalies and anomaly explanation. The authors also categorized existing deep learning anomaly detection methods into three categories: (1) generic normality feature learning (e.g., autoencoders, GANs), (2) measure-dependent normality feature learning (e.g., clustering, one-class classification) and (3) end-to-end anomaly score learning (e.g., anomaly ranking models). The article also emphasizes self-supervised learning approaches for generic normality feature learning that is based on the assumption that normal data instances are more consistent to self-supervised classifiers than anomalies.

The main challenge in supervised anomaly detection approaches is the problem of class imbalance that can be tackled either at the data level (e.g., by undersampling or oversampling data algorithms) or the algorithm level (e.g., by cost-sensitive machine learning algorithms). Anomaly detection with incomplete supervision refers to the situation where only part of the input data is labeled, so fully-supervised models do not apply. Jiang et al. (2023) [JHZ23] presents key methods for semi-supervised anomaly detection emphasizing that those approaches belong to the following categories: feature representation learning and anomaly score learning as previously categorized by Pang et al. (2020) [PSC21], but also methods based on graph-neural networks, active and reinforcement learning.

Traditional supervised machine learning approaches follow the closed-world assumption stating that the set of categories/labels is fully known at the model training time. Consequently, such machine learning models at the inference time fail to identify classes which were not available during the training time. It should be emphasized that the closed-world assumption is often reasonable in scenarios where possible classes are well-defined and unlikely to change over time.

However, in dynamic and open environments, characterized with unexpected situations, instances belonging to previously unseen classes may appear. This and related issues are addressed by open-world machine learning algorithms [SMH22; PCR23] that are conceptually similar to anomaly detection algorithms. There are two main categories of open-world machine learning methods: out-of-distribution (OOD) detection and open set recognition (OSR).

OOD aims to detect at the inference time data points that belong to a distribution that is different from the training distribution. The article by Yang et al. (2024) [YZL24] gives a comprehensive overview of OOD methods that are categorized into the following four categories: classification-based methods, density-based methods, distance-based methods and reconstruction-based methods. Classification-based approaches are either post-hoc methods giving OOD scores without interfering with classification learning (e.g., ODIN), methods that use specialized training objectives (e.g., generalized ODIN), methods with outlier exposure where outliers can be either real or synthetic, and gradient-based methods deriving OOD scores from the gradient space (e.g., GradNorm). Density-based methods model the in-distribution with a probabilistic model. Data instances residing in low-density regions are then marked as OOD instances. The basic idea of distance-based methods is that OOD samples reside relatively far away from centroids of in-distribution classes. The core idea of reconstruction-based methods is that autoencoder architectures trained on the ID data gives different reconstruction errors for ID and OOD instances.

Machine learning models trained in the closed-world setting can incorrectly classify data instances from unknown classes as one of the known categories with high confidence. This issue is addressed by OSR methods. Zhu et al. (2024) [ZMC24] divided OSR methods into three categories: discriminative models, generative models and hybrid models (i.e., models that combine discriminative and generative models). Discriminative models are mainly based on support vector machines, nearest class classifiers, extreme value machines, neural networks with recalibrated weights and autoencoders. Generative models rely on synthetically generated pseudo-unknown samples to augment classifiers.

After detecting unknown data instances by OOD or OSR techniques, those data instances should be labeled by humans or novel class discovery strategies. Novel class discovery in essence is a clustering task on a set of unknown data instances continually collected at the inference time. Then the system must continually extend its predictive models to learn newly identified classes, which is known as class-incremental learning (CIL), being the last step in the open-world machine learning process [ZMC24].

Conclusions

The state-of-the-art supervised machine and deep learning methods usually follow the closed-world assumption, which states that the complete set of data categories (classes or labels) is fully known at model training time. Consequently, the corresponding predictive models fail to identify novel or unknown classes at inference time. This problem is addressed by so-called open-world class incremental learning (CIL) methods that involve appropriate novelty detection (ND) models. Although many CIL and ND algorithms have been proposed in the literature, they still have certain limitations, especially in continual learning settings. The first limitation is that the number of novel classes should be known a-priori. The second limitation is related to the separation of novelties from outliers. Namely, what is an outlier in the current data batch may not be an outlier after seeing the next data batches. One of the main scientific challenges in the PANDORA project will be to devise continual, self-validated learning methods that follow the open-world assumption in order to have robust model learning and resilient model inference. This means that continuous learning methods should be accompanied with novelty detection at model training time (robust learning) and outlier detection at model inference time (resilient inference), that also must be continuously updated and self-validated.

4.3.2 Continuous Self-Validated Learning for Improved Long-Term Autonomy and Intelligence

Continual learning provides a foundation for ML-based systems to develop themselves adaptively. This means that a predictive model is learning from non-stationary data streams and it is continuously updated on data batches as new training data points become available [VTT22]. As data batches (also called tasks) are provided incrementally over a lifetime, continual learning is in the literature also referred to as incremental learning or lifelong learning [P19]. Several machine learning models are by design suitable for continual learning, most notably neural networks and other methods based on stochastic gradient optimization. One of the major challenges in continual learning arises from the sequential nature of learning and it is manifested by the so-called catastrophic forgetting [L22], where learning on new data batches may result in a significant performance degradation of the predictive model on old data batches. This negative phenomenon can be avoided by retraining the model using all old training data points, but this creates huge computational and storage overheads. The continuous learning model has to maintain a good degree of balance between plasticity (the ability to adapt to new knowledge) and stability (the ability to retain prior knowledge) [Sa22]. Consequently, it is important to evaluate the performance of continual learning considering following aspects: overall predictive performance on both old and new data batches (e.g., average accuracy and average incremental accuracy metrics), memory stability of old data batches (e.g., forgetting measure and backward transfer metrics) and learning plasticity of new data batches (e.g., intransience and forward transfer metrics) [WZS24]. De Lange et al. (2022) [L22] indicate ten desirable properties of general continual learning systems:

1. constant memory (the consumed memory should be constant with respect to the number of data batches and their lengths),
2. no task boundaries (the system should not require clear task divisions),
3. online training (the system should not demand offline training),
4. forward transfer (previously acquired knowledge should aid the learning of new tasks),
5. backward transfer (previously acquired knowledge should be retained or even improved when learning on new tasks),
6. problem agnostic (continual learning should not be limited to a specific machine learning task, e.g. only classification),
7. learning from unlabeled data,
8. no test time oracle (task labels should not be required when performing inference),
9. task revisiting (previously seen tasks should enable enhancements of newly learned tasks), and
10. graceful forgetting (selective forgetting of trivial information could achieve balance between stability and plasticity).

There are five principal approaches to continual learning: replay-based, regularization-based, optimization-based, representation-based and architecture-based [WZS24]. The main idea of *replay-based approaches* is to recover old data distributions by keeping a certain fraction of old data instances or by having a model that generates synthetic data points from old distributions. Such data points are then included when updating the model on a new training batch. In *regularization-based* approaches a copy of the old model is used to regularize parameters when training on new data batches, usually in some form of Bayesian learning framework. In *optimization-based* approaches, gradient directions of new data points are forced to stay close to gradient directions of few old training data points that are kept in a memory buffer or, alternatively, gradient projections of old training data points are performed without storing old data.

Representation-based approaches rely on pre-training and self-supervised learning to derive latent data representations that are robust to distribution differences across data batches. Finally, in the architecture-based approaches new tasks (corresponding to new data batches) are incrementally learned by introducing new task-specific model parameters alongside the task-shared model parameters.

Depending on the target of regularization, regularization-based approaches can be further divided into *weight-regularization* methods and *function-regularization* methods [WZS24]. In weight-regularization methods, a penalty is incorporated into the loss function to minimize the variation of each parameter proportionally to its impact on the model's predictive performance on old data batches [K17]. *Function-regularization* methods are based on the teacher-student learning paradigm and knowledge distillation techniques [KPH22] to mitigate catastrophic forgetting during continual learning.

Replay-based approaches can be further divided into three sub-categories: experience replay, generative replay and feature replay methods [WZS24]. Experience replay methods store a certain fraction of old data points in a small memory buffer [R19]. The main issue with those methods is how to select old data points for the buffer. Several strategies are proposed in the literature [WZS24]: reservoir sampling, mean-of-feature, strategies based on k-means, plane distance and entropy, mini-batch gradient similarity, cross-batch gradient diversity, etc. Generative replay methods (also known as pseudo-rehearsal methods) train an additional generative model that is used to synthesize data points similar to the old ones [S17]. Various types of generative models could be used for pseudo-rehearsal, such as generative adversarial networks and variational autoencoders. Feature replay methods [La20] are similar to generative replays methods with the difference that they are focused on replaying data representations (instead of data points).

Self-supervised learning or pre-training are used in representation-based methods to obtain latent data representations that bring not only strong knowledge transfer, but also robustness to catastrophic forgetting [Zb24]. Self-supervised learning with contrastive loss is typically used in continual learning scenarios [WZS24].

In contrast to the previously described methods having one shared set of model parameters for all data batches, architecture-based methods introduce task-specific model parameters. Those methods can be divided into three sub-categories: (1) parameter allocation methods, (2) model decomposition networks and (3) modular networks [WZS24]. In parameter allocation methods, independent parts of model parameters are allocated to different data batches, so that the parameters of the allocated part are updated on the current data batch, while the rest of the parameters are frozen (or nearly frozen). Model decomposition methods separate the model into task-sharing and task-specific components where task-specific components are typically expandable. Finally, modular networks [V20] use parallel sub-networks allowing knowledge transfer via adaptor connections.

There are also several empirical analyses of continual learning methods investigating the impact of catastrophic forgetting. As indicated by Zhao et al. (2023) [Za23] for various neural network based continuous learning methods, only a few parameters change more significantly than others between incremental data batches. Therefore, most parameters of the model can be shared across data batches and it is necessary to finetune a few task-specific parameters to retain good performance on old data batches.

In contrast to numerous machine learning model validation methodologies proposed in the literature (e.g., training test validation splits, k-fold cross validation, leave one out cross validation), self-validation capabilities of machine learning systems are not yet thoroughly investigated. As two paradigmatic studies in this direction we mention two works by Savić et al. (2021, 2022) [Sb21; S22] in the field of anomaly detection that indicate two principal approaches

to self-validation. The first approach [Sb21] is to use a sequence of increasingly complex models (e.g. neural networks with increasingly complex model architectures), where each subsequent model can check and validate inference results of the previous model in the sequence in the case of unsatisfactory prediction confidence scores. The second approach [Sb22] is to employ hybrid machine learning methods combining different machine learning designs. In this approach, predictions of a high-precision model are validated against predictions made by a high-recall model.

Conclusion

Our literature review indicates that there are plenty of continual learning methods. However, a majority of them are designed only for classification problems, whereas in the AIoT domain regression and (unsupervised) anomaly detection are more prevailing machine learning problems. Secondly, existing solutions do not have self-validating capabilities, nor are they robust and resilient to non-stationary outliers. All previously mentioned issues will be addressed in the PANDORA project. Additionally, we will propose continuous learning methods that work on compact data representations obtained by federated learning.

As already emphasized, a large body of research works are related to model validation, but the issue of self-validation is not thoughtfully investigated. There are two principal approaches to self-validation: (1) sequential ensembles and (2) ensembles combining different machine learning designs. Both approaches were previously investigated and utilized only for anomaly detection problems, not for classification and regression. Thus, in the PANDORA project we will investigate how those two types of ensembles suitable for self-validation can be adapted for relevant AIoT machine learning tasks.

4.3.3 Hybrid Learning and Reasoning for Domain-Informed, Causal, and Explainable AI with Multiple Continuous Learning Methods

Explainable AI (XAI) for time series data seeks to make model predictions transparent and interpretable in critical applications like predictive maintenance and system monitoring. Specifically in the domain of IoT applications, IoT devices continuously generate time-dependent data, such as sensor readings from industrial machines, robots, or environmental sensors, where detecting anomalies, estimating energy consumption or delays, or predicting failures is essential for preventing costly downtime or safety risks. XAI techniques help understand why a certain sensor reading or sequence is flagged as anomalous or indicative of failure, highlighting critical time points, patterns, drifts or trends that trigger the alert. Explanations can further be enhanced with elements from existing domain knowledge or causal relations derived from historical data for a more semantic interpretation of the prediction. By providing insights into the factors leading to these predictions, XAI builds trust, aids in root cause analysis, and allows operators to take timely, informed actions. In this section, we give an overview of the state of the art on post-hoc Explainable AI focusing on the tasks of Anomaly Detection and Multivariate Time Series Classification, representing unsupervised and supervised machine learning respectively.

Explainable Anomaly Detection (xAD) and Predictive Maintenance (PM)

Detecting and diagnosing data anomalies are important tasks in data processing pipelines used to build industrial-strength AI systems. Clearly, data points that significantly deviate from other points in a dataset may be systematic errors, i.e., outliers, or may manifest changes in the data generation process per se, i.e., novelties, that decrease the accuracy of the predictive models constructed downstream [NW12]. In scientific and industrial monitoring applications, anomaly detection is often the ultimate goal of the data analysis as it enables the identification of unusual measurements (e.g., related to faults, bio-indices, etc.) and/or of suspicious activities (e.g. intrusions, fraud, etc.). Additionally to anomaly diagnosis, in Predictive Maintenance we are

interested in predicting *when a fault will arise in the future*. Several unsupervised algorithms for anomaly detection have been proposed [A13, ZF18] using different methods (e.g., proximity or isolation based) to distinguish outliers from inliers when labels of data points are impossible or difficult to obtain, as well as algorithms tailored to predicting failures in the case of sparse data points recording failures [AAF18]. Unfortunately, these algorithms do not explain why a data point was considered as abnormal, leaving analysts with no guidance about where to begin their investigation.

[MCS21] provides a thorough experimental evaluation of existing algorithms explaining the outlyingness aspects of multi-dimensional data points in the form of subspaces of data features that best explain why a given outlier deviates the most from the inliers. Such explanations are crucial to diagnose the root cause of data anomalies [AGJ13] and enable corrective actions to prevent or remedy their effect in downstream data processing (e.g. by repairing data errors or retraining the predictive models for concept drifts). As no detector is good for all possible characteristics of datasets (see the conclusions of several experimental studies [CZS16, DFM18]), we are interested in decoupling the outlier explanation from detection. In this respect we are focusing in unsupervised algorithms that are both domain-agnostic (i.e., suitable for datasets from various domains) and detector-agnostic (i.e., they can be employed to explain outliers produced by any off-the-self detector).

Anomaly explanations usually take the form of feature subsets of significantly lower dimensionality compared to the original data space. By examining only the features of an explaining subspace suffices to determine whether a sample is an anomaly or not according to a detector. Explanations can be categorized as (i) descriptive in the sense that they explain the samples used to train the detector and (ii) predictive that generalize to unseen data. For instance, a descriptive explanation can be expressed as the subset of features of the training data that best explains a detected anomaly. A predictive explanation can be expressed as the feature space hyperplane that leads to an optimal reduced model, thus being able to predict future anomalies. As descriptive explanation methods need to be recomputed for every new batch of data [MTC21, MTC24] proposes PROTEUS for producing global, predictive explanations using a surrogate model. As experimentally proven, PROTEUS is not only able to discover explaining subspaces of features relevant to anomalies, but it can also construct predictive models that approximate effectively and robustly the decision boundary of popular unsupervised detectors (e.g., IF, LOF, LODA).

Explainable Multivariate Time Series Classification (xTSC)

Multivariate Time Series (MTS) are omnipresent in many science and engineering domains, including health-care, sustainable energy, geoscience, and high-performance computing. An MTS is composed of more than one time-dependent variables that may depend not only on its past values but also on other variables. Neural Network (NN) architectures (e.g., TCNN [BMR22], LSTM [HS97] Transformer [VSP17]) are state-of-the-art solutions in order to implement MTS Classification [NAD22], [FFW19], [IGC20]. Deep NN models are essentially uninterpretable black boxes, where one feeds an input and obtains an output without understanding the motivations behind that decision. We have recently witnessed a consistent effort to enhance NN models with explanation capabilities at various levels allowing users to track the time-dependent variables or the training timestamped samples that drive a NN model toward a certain decision. Specifically, eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (xAI) techniques such as dCAM [BMR22], XCM [FLM21], Dynamask [CS21], TimeSHAP [BSC21] aim to reveal which subsets of MTS variables are mostly involved in deciding a particular class label.

Post-hoc explanation methods like feature attribution [RSG16], [LL17] or saliency maps [SVZ14] can help indicate which features or pixels of input data are most 'relevant' to the output decision of a NN model being 'explained'. However, they are designed with the assumption that a single sample is self-explanatory and analysts can easily distinguish between two samples, which is not

easy in complex MTS with thousands of time-dependent variables. Additionally, the intrinsic measures underlying xAI methods are purely associational and may expose potentially spurious and misleading correlations in input data used to train a NN model. Clearly, correlation-based explanations are not informative enough in order to produce surrogate models of reduced complexity (i.e., by projecting input data on the relevant features) or to debug models (e.g., by identifying data instances and/or model components that cause incorrect predictions).

These kinds of tasks call for more expressive forms of explanations, which can reveal causal-effect relationships between TS variables (input or target) along with adequate lag information. Causal explanations are usually distinguished between sufficient explanations and counterfactual explanations [B22]. The former permits users to understand the conditions in which a particular action (e.g., selecting a subset of TS variables as predictors) will produce a desired model outcome. The latter instead identifies actions (e.g., changing the values of TS variables) that can alter an observed input, ensuring a change in a previously observed output. According to the recent empirical study [VAL23] surrogate models built over causal relationships outperform not only models built over relevant features detected by xAI methods such as dCAM [BMR22], XCM [FLM21], Dynamask [CS21], TimeSHAP [BSC21] but also advanced NN models trained over the whole data feature space. A different approach to obtaining local surrogate models around a point of interest is by finding the most appropriate GENEOS operators from a predefined library.

Conclusion

The current state-of-the-art methods in anomaly detection and multivariate time-series classification demonstrate that causal explanations are the most effective and actionable for both explaining the root causes of predictions and proposing surrogate models that can locally substitute the predictive model. In our continuous IoT setting, data or model drifts need to be accounted in the explanations, in combination with the potentially evolving domain knowledge. Finally, explainability techniques built on supervised tasks involve mostly classification, however regression tasks or unsupervised tasks with sparse error occurrences correspond best to predictive maintenance.

4.3.4 Federated Representational Learning for Efficient Data Formats

Federated learning (FL) [K21] has emerged as a decentralized learning paradigm for training machine learning (ML) models across multiple clients (edge nodes). FL differs from standard distributed learning in that data is never centralized, as it is collected at the edge. This provides numerous benefits, some of the most important being increased security and privacy, and the reduction of communication overhead needed to centralize the data or to distribute initially centralized data across a cluster of workers. In most cases, the FL process is coordinated by a central server which conducts client selection and model aggregation. The model aggregation function is one of the key concepts in FL. Following each global learning step, the clients submit their locally updated models to the server.

Different model aggregation functions like FedAvg, FedProx, and FedHybrid [Lb20], [M17], [NW23] can yield substantially different updated global models. Apart from the aggregation function, optimal client selection and the model updating strategy also play a significant role in the quality of the global models obtained through FL. The effects of having incremental or concurrent model updates have been explored in [IIK24], [S23], [S20], [SR18]. The aim of FL is to train global models which generalize well on the entirety of the distributed dataset. However, as no assumptions can be made on the distributions from which the data was drawn at each individual node, there is a significant challenge in balancing between the model's generalizability and its effectiveness at each individual edge node. To solve this model personalization problem,

solutions like client clustering, multi-task learning, and local fine tuning have been proposed [ABJ22], [FMO20], [HR20], [LFT20], [SMS20], [SCS17], [W19].

Representational learning (RL) is a technique which involves learning how to extract relevant features from inputs to ML models during training and inference. By doing so, generalizable features from the original input dataset can be obtained. Carrying valuable information, they can then be used for multiple related inference tasks. RL algorithms learn representations that capture underlying factors, allowing this knowledge to be transferable to multiple learning tasks [BCV13]. Learning representations can be done in numerous ways, one of the most prominent being by utilizing deep neural networks, called autoencoders [BCV13] consisting of two parts: the encoder and the decoder. RL consists of two parts, first, learning the representation and mapping the inputs to a latent space, while the second part includes utilizing the encoder with different network heads for various inference tasks [RBL07], [SÖL19]. In most cases, learning representations of input features is done in unsupervised, semi-supervised, or self-supervised [BCV13], [DSR14], [SÖL19] manners. It is argued that the curation of large-scale datasets is costly and time-consuming and is also a particularly challenging task for domains like medicine, as it requires domain expertise.

Federated representation learning (FRL) is a concept joining federated and representational learning. The motivation behind this lies in the fact that data distributions among clients may differ substantially. As such, the learning task at each individual edge node may be framed as a multi-task learning problem. In this regard, learning an abstract representation of the distributed dataset can increase the performance of models across the entire system. In the majority of cases, FL models are deep neural networks as aggregation of the learned weights is relatively straightforward. In this regard, FRL also sees frequent use of autoencoder networks [NFG23], [P21], [BSÖ20], [Zb23] for learning representations in federated environments. The representations obtained from these methods support subsequent training of ML models for classification and regression tasks on this data.

Alternatively, the autoencoder models learned in this unsupervised manner can also be used for outlier detection tasks. The premise is that the reconstruction error of previously unseen (outlier) instances will have a greater error than the reconstruction error from similar (inlier) data points. Unsupervised anomaly detection in federated settings has been explored and key research directions have been found in [AMH24]. In these experiments, five different models were validated on 4 datasets. The models include: deep autoencoders [CYL18], deep structured energy-based models [ZCL16], deep one-class classification [R18], neural transformation learning with deep networks [QPK21], and memory augmented deep autoencoders [GLL19]. Through these experiments, a benchmark for validating the performance of anomaly detection models in federated settings has been set in place. A key research direction that has been identified in this paper is the need for the advancement of aggregation functions for unsupervised anomaly detection models.

Conclusion

Based on the literature review conducted on the state-of-the-art in terms of federated learning and representational learning, a couple of key observations can be made. There are numerous use cases in which federated learning can be utilized in order to obtain quality models, where it is impossible to centralize the learning process for reasons such as security and privacy, computational complexity, or it simply being impractical. In this regard, FL offers an alternative approach to distributed learning which yields models comparable in performance to centralized models, even surpassing them in certain scenarios.

Representational learning is an approach to learning abstract representations of the data domain, with the goal being to generalize the knowledge encoded in the data in order to be able to perform well on a diverse set of inference tasks, which is also referred to as multi-task learning. In terms

of the data distribution between edge nodes which can vary significantly, this learning task is similar to the multi-task learning problem. Consequently, learning representations in federated settings can help make these models more robust.

4.3.5 Continual Inference Networks for Faster Deep Learning Model Processing

Recently, efficient methods have been proposed that optimize the process of sequential data analysis through Deep Learning models. Sequential data can be defined as any type data whose elements can be arranged in some logical linear order, the most natural form of such an order being time. For example, a video is a sequence of images (also called frames) which are arranged temporarily. Processing of sequential data with state-of-the-art Deep Learning models poses a great challenge, especially when the amount of data received in the items forming the sequence (which we will refer to as sequence items) is high.

Multiple Deep Learning models have been proposed for processing sequential data. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) process each input sequence item and combine prior processing results by computational units having recurrency properties. Due to the recurrency in their computations, processing of the input sequence needs to be done in a sequential manner and, thus, acceleration practices offered by parallel processing units cannot be fully exploited. Some recent works have addressed this limitation for image [AAF19] and video segmentation [PD19]. Other works combine recurrent processing blocks with popular attention mechanisms [TPT22].

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [LBD89] have been successfully applied in image analysis problems [Z18] [JT19] [AAF19] by processing their input in such a way that the local features get extracted first and patterns of local features combined in a hierarchical manner at multiple processing layers for extracting data representations suitable for solving complex classification and regression tasks. This is achieved by applying multiple sets of 2D filters at several processing layers. This approach has also been exploited for processing time-series, such as in audio processing [PD19] where the input time-series data can be converted into an image displaying the corresponding spectrogram. The temporal dimension present in multi-dimensional time-series data such as videos can also be processed by extending the 2D filtering operation in standard CNNs to three dimensions leading to the 3D CNNs [TPT22], where time is added as a new dimension, and the filters are expanded accordingly [LBD89] enabling processing and extracting temporal patterns appearing between adjacent sequence items. When adequate training data is available, the adoption of 3D CNNs has shown to outperform Deep Learning models combining sequence item processing, e.g., through 2D CNNs, with recurrent processing blocks.

Transformers [VSP17] is another Deep Learning model which has been widely used for different analysis problems and are the main component behind the most recent advances in Large-Language Processing [BMR20] and Computer Vision [DBK21] models. Extensions of the original Transformer architecture have also been applied with success in problems involving [ADH21]. However, they have a computational cost scaling in a quadratic manner with respect to the size of their input and (in general) they require much larger datasets compared to prior Deep Learning model architectures for achieving competitive performance, limiting their applicability to different problems where large amounts of data are not available or when the size of the input data is large. Modifications to the Transformer architecture have been proposed, which try to address high computational cost when the input data size is large by reducing the practical size of the data matrices involved in the core operation of the Transformer architecture, i.e., the Self-Attention. These include the Sparse Transformer [CGR19] which performs computations related to inputs coming from neighboring input frames as well as some sparse connections with inputs coming from further away frames. Similarly, Performers [CLD21] limit the number of matrix multiplications depending on a random feature map. Architectures based on low-rank matrix approximation schemes have also been proposed, which rely on mathematical assumptions to reduce the size

of matrix multiplications involved in the Self-Attention mechanism, such as the Linformer [WLK20] and the Nyströmformer [XZC21]. Several methods also apply the attention mechanisms for multivariate [CIGa22] and multimodal [CIGb22] contexts

Even though efficient variants of the Deep Learning models tailored to sequence data analysis have led to efficient solutions, when continual data stream is needed, they lead to inefficient solutions. This is because they need to be combined with a temporal rolling window processing scheme, applying the Deep Learning model multiple times, i.e., at the sequence clip determined by the position of the rolling window over time, leading to redundant computations. For example, when processing the visual stream captured by a camera using a rolling window with size of 100 frames and step size of 1, each image captured by the camera will be introduced to the Deep Learning model 100 times. This leads to the case where the visual stream cannot be processed in real-time, even when the adopted Deep Learning model can process video clips formed by 100 images in real time.

To address this issue, a new family of models has been recently proposed specifically tailored to sequential data analysis called Continual Inference Networks (CINs) [HBI23]. CINs are Deep Learning models which:

- are capable of continual step inference without computational redundancy,
- are capable of batch inference corresponding to a non-continual Neural Network,
- produce identical outputs for batch- and step inference given identical receptive fields, and
- use one set of trainable parameters for both batch and step inference.

CINs are designed to process sequential data in an item-by-item manner, by reusing prior computations in such a way that in every iteration only the newest sequence item is processed. This makes them an excellent candidate for continual stream data processing, where new input data arrive at fixed intervals or by-demand, enabling high accelerations compared to their non-continual counterparts. Specific CIN instantiations are the Continual 3D Convolutional Neural Networks (Co-3DCNN) [Hla22] leading to one order of magnitude reduction in the number of computations compared to their non-continual counterpart, the Continual Transformers [HBI23] which achieve linear cost in Transformer by reusing prior computations, offering the same performance at two-order of magnitude reduction in the number of computations, and the Continual Spatio-Temporal Graph Convolutional networks [Hlb22] and their simplifications[YFM24] leading to a reduction of up to three orders of magnitude in the number of computations compared to their non-continual versions.

Conclusion

While the adoption of lightweight Deep Learning models and Deep Learning models equipped with recurrency mechanisms can lead to efficient processing of static data (e.g., images) and short-term sequence data (e.g., video clips of short duration), processing of stream data like visual streams and multidimensional time-series streams with high-performing Deep Learning architectures (like 3D CNNs and Transformers) is computationally complex due to the need to perform computations in a rolling window manner leading to redundant computations. The recently introduced Continual Inference Networks provide a solution to this limitation by transforming the computations conducted by such high-performing Deep Learning models to their continual form. While this has shown to lead to considerable reductions in the computational complexity sacrificing much in performance, new methodological advancements in the architectural designs of such networks and in their training processes can potentially lead to further improvements making them a viable solution for efficient stream data processing.

4.3.6 Adaptive Distribution and Optimization of AI Inference Using Cloud-Edge Integration

Adaptive and distributed inference in cloud-edge computing involves various techniques to optimize deep learning (DL) models for resource-constrained environments and balance AI workloads between cloud and edge resources. Key strategies include:

1. **Model Adaptation for Edge Deployment:** Model adaptation methods address constraints in computing power, memory, and bandwidth by employing **model compression** techniques like pruning, quantization, knowledge distillation, and low-rank factorization, which reduce model size and resource usage [HAB21], [LGW21], [SCG19], [SGK20]. Alternatively, **conditional computation** techniques such as early exit, model selection, and result caching dynamically adjust complexity based on available resources or task requirements, lowering latency and energy consumption [BBP15], [SSB20].
2. **Edge-Level Model Training:** Efficient training methods like **model parallelism** split Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) across multiple edge resources to optimize computational load [SPP19]. Other approaches include **aggregation frequency control (AFC)** to minimize communication costs [JHT23], **gossip training** to enhance fault tolerance [BPC16], [STE20], and **gradient compression** to reduce bandwidth usage [ACB21]. Techniques like **data parallelism**, **federated learning (FL)**, and **split learning** allow distributed and privacy-preserving training by partitioning data or model computations across edge resources [TAC22].
3. **Cloud-Edge Integration for Adaptive Inference:** Cloud-edge collaboration leverages cloud resources for training complex models while enabling real-time inference at the edge. This distribution reduces latency and improves efficiency, particularly in time-sensitive applications [LDX23]. Emerging frameworks dynamically partition tasks between cloud, edge servers, and edge devices based on latency prediction and resource availability [RCV22]. The deployment of **5G technology** enhances communication efficiency, critical for applications like augmented reality and industrial automation [YJW24].
4. **Orchestration and Federated Learning:** Orchestration platforms such as KubeEdge and EdgeX Foundry automate task distribution across the cloud-edge continuum, ensuring scalability and adaptability. **Federated learning** enables collaborative model training across edge devices without transferring sensitive data, improving privacy and reducing bandwidth usage.
5. **Optimization Techniques for Edge Devices:** Model optimization strategies like pruning, quantization, and neural architecture search (NAS) reduce complexity and energy consumption, essential for battery-powered devices. Advanced techniques like **Receptive Field-based Segmentation (RFS)** and **Host-Assisted Layer-wise Parallelization (HALP)** further enhance distributed inference by reducing communication overhead and optimizing CNN layer execution [DLI22], [LLZa22], [LLZb22]. Additionally, novel methods like **position-wise layer partitioning** distribute Transformer model workloads efficiently across edge devices [HLB24].
6. **Self-Adaptive AI Infrastructures:** Future cloud-edge systems are expected to incorporate self-adaptive mechanisms, leveraging predictive models to autonomously adjust resource allocation and task distribution in response to changing conditions. This level of intelligence is essential for critical applications in autonomous driving, industrial IoT, and infrastructure monitoring.

Conclusions

In conclusion, adaptive and distributed inference in cloud-edge computing has made significant strides in optimizing deep learning models for resource-limited environments while effectively balancing AI workloads across cloud and edge resources. Techniques such as model adaptation, compression, and conditional computation enable efficient deployment on edge devices, minimizing energy and latency concerns. Edge-level training approaches, including model and data parallelism, federated learning, and gradient compression, facilitate distributed training and maintain data privacy. Cloud-edge integration, enhanced by 5G technology, provides robust frameworks for real-time, low-latency inference crucial for applications like augmented reality and industrial automation. Orchestration platforms and advanced optimization methods further streamline resource management and scalability, while self-adaptive infrastructures promise future systems that can autonomously respond to dynamic conditions. These innovations collectively shape a future where cloud-edge synergy supports increasingly sophisticated, responsive, and energy-efficient AI systems, essential for emerging technologies and critical real-world applications.

4.3.7 Research Gaps

The identified research gaps in the field of AI and machine learning highlight several critical areas for advancement. In the realm of Open-World Learning and Novelty Detection, there is a need for methods that can identify novel classes without prior knowledge of their number and improve the separation of novelties from outliers, acknowledging that an outlier in one context may not be in another. Continual Learning and Self-Validation require robust methods that incorporate novelty detection during training and outlier detection during inference, alongside self-validating models that can continuously adapt and validate themselves. Extending these methods beyond classification to regression and unsupervised anomaly detection is crucial, particularly in the AIoT domain, as is the development of continual learning techniques compatible with federated learning's compact data representations. Advanced self-validation approaches, such as sequential ensembles and the combination of high-precision and high-recall models, are also essential for ensuring reliable performance across the edge-fog-cloud computing continuum.

Additionally, in the area of Causal Explanations and Model Adaptation, there is a need for efficient methods to enumerate and rank causal models based on user preferences and needs, as well as dynamic causal models that can compute explanations for similar data points over time, considering data and model drifts in IoT scenarios. Actionable Explanations, particularly counterfactual explanations for 'What-if' analysis, are necessary to aid expert decision-making, as typical feature-relevance explanations are not actionable. Investigating explanation methods for regression tasks, especially for predictive maintenance, is essential to address diverse application areas beyond the commonly addressed classification tasks.

In the domain of Federated Learning (FL), developing models for scenarios where centralizing the learning process is impractical due to security, privacy, or computational complexity is crucial. Enhancing FL models to achieve or surpass the performance of centralized models is another significant challenge. Representational Learning (RL) in federated settings requires the creation of robust representations to handle varying data distributions across edge nodes and the generalization of knowledge to perform well on diverse inference tasks, akin to multi-task learning. Federated Representational Learning (FRL) calls for exploring attention-based models, particularly for outlier detection, and developing new aggregation functions suitable for these models.

Furthermore, in the area of Sequence Processing in AIoT, there is a need to focus on reducing the dimensionality of matrices and other elements in sequence processing, and to address the computational redundancies caused by combining dimensionality reduction with rolling window

processes. Continual Inference requires the development of continual inference versions of approximate schemes to reduce computational redundancies in processing long sequences.

In the context of Scalability and Real-Time Performance, developing scalable architectures that maintain real-time capabilities across different levels (edge to cloud) in heterogeneous environments is essential. Optimizing techniques like model compression, quantization, and federated learning for deployment on resource-constrained IoT devices is also critical. Security and Privacy demand the creation of holistic security frameworks to safeguard both AI models and IoT infrastructure from attacks, and the development of interoperable standards for seamless communication and integration across diverse AIoT platforms. Lifecycle Management involves developing frameworks for automated, zero-touch lifecycle management, including model updates, fault detection, and system reconfiguration, as well as creating energy-efficient AIoT frameworks to optimize AI inference and communication for long-term sustainability. Context-Aware and Adaptive Models require the development of AI models that adapt to changing environmental conditions and contexts in real-time, and the embedding of ethical considerations into AIoT systems to ensure transparency, accountability, and fairness.

Finally, in the area of Distributed Inference for DAGs, there is a need to develop methods to adapt distributed inference to directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) due to their complex layer dependencies, and to ensure correct execution order in DAGs, where layers can have multiple predecessors or successors. Efficient Data Distribution and Communication involve creating efficient data distribution schemes to handle scattered input data across different devices and reducing communication overhead caused by inefficient partition schemes for layers distributed across multiple devices. These gaps underscore the need for innovative solutions to enhance the adaptability, robustness, and reliability of AI systems in diverse and dynamic environments.

5. Legal and ethical requirements

5.1 Introduction

As AIoT systems get increasingly integrated into critical sectors, they offer transformative potential but also pose significant ethical and legal risks, necessitating careful consideration of the requirements for their responsible deployment. While legal requirements, as enforced by competent regulatory bodies, carry formal consequences for non-compliance, ethical requirements urge us to voluntarily act in certain ways. They stem from moral reasoning about what is right, good, or beneficial for society and individuals grounded in principles and rights of personality that reflect the moral axiom of universal respect for persons' dignity. Given that AI legislation is still in its early stages, emerging laws, policies and standards have been heavily influenced by ongoing ethical research and guidelines aimed at fostering trust and responsible decision-making in the field.

Focusing predominantly on EU sources, this section presents a preliminary investigation of the ethical and legal landscape in need of consideration in the design and development of the PANDORA framework. Section 5.2 presents an overview of key European Union (EU) regulations, directives, and guidelines, alongside relevant international recommendations and standards, whereas Section 5.3 enlists related compliance assessment frameworks. Section 5.4 provides a literature overview, discussing relevant challenges related to the normative framework for AI governance. Section 5.5 briefly discusses the need for the conduction of surveys for gathering insights regarding legal and ethical considerations pertinent to PANDORA and Section 5.6 concludes this part of the deliverable.

5.2 Regulatory framework

Conformity with ethical principles and relevant Union, national and international legislation, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols, constitutes a horizontal legal obligation for all Horizon Europe beneficiaries, as provisioned in art. 19 of the Regulation (EU) 2021/695, as well as a contractual commitment of the PANDORA consortium (under Grant Agreement 'GA', No. 101135775), as explicitly acknowledged in Art. 14 of the PANDORA GA.

The main identified areas of interest in the case of PANDORA are AI governance and cybersecurity. Relevant requirements have been embedded in the applicable EU secondary law, such as the recently adopted AI Act, the Cybersecurity Act, the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 GDPR, amongst other. Forthcoming developments in the EU regulatory landscape need also to be considered as the project progresses, including, for example, the proposal for the EU Cyber Resilience Act. It is noted that, if throughout the project any updates or changes in relevant legislation, ethical guidelines or planned use cases occur, they will be correspondingly incorporated into relevant project documentation.

5.2.1 EU Regulations and Directives

Artificial Intelligence

The EU AI Act constitutes the first comprehensive, horizontal legal framework specifically tailored to regulate artificial intelligence (AI). At its core, the AI Act adopts a technologically neutral definition of AI systems, framing them as machine-based systems designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and adaptiveness after deployment, and to generate outputs – inferred from the input they receive and for explicit or implicit objectives, such as predictions, content, or decisions that influence both physical and virtual environments (AI Act, Art. 3(1)).

The Act employs a risk-based regulatory approach, categorizing AI systems into four risk levels: unacceptable (i.e., pose a clear threat to the safety, livelihoods, and rights of individuals, such as those used for social scoring or exploitative behavioral manipulation), high (i.e., can significantly impact fundamental rights, safety, or critical infrastructure), limited (such as chatbots or deep fakes, requiring specific transparency obligations), and minimal or no risk.

A notable feature of the AI Act is its extra-territorial scope, applying to AI systems that impact EU residents regardless of where the provider¹ is located, thus setting a global benchmark for trustworthy AI, similar to the GDPR’s extraterritorial impact on data protection. The Act also introduces mechanisms such as the European AI Board, which will oversee its implementation and promote cooperation among national regulators to ensure consistent enforcement, and supports the use of regulatory sandboxes, allowing for the controlled testing of AI systems to foster innovation while maintaining compliance with ethical and legal standards.

The following table provides key information on the AI Act’s provisions and relevance to PANDORA.

Table 2: Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 (AI Act)

The Artificial Intelligence Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689, ‘AI Act’) ²	
Status	Entered into force on 1st August 2024 and will apply from 2 August 2026 ³ , except for the specific provisions listed in its Art. 113. Amongst other, these exemptions include the prohibition of AI practices provisioned in Chapter II, which will apply from 2 February 2025, while the classification rules for high-risk AI systems and the corresponding obligations set by the regulation shall apply from 2 August 2027.
Purpose	To improve the functioning of the internal market and promote the uptake of human-centric and trustworthy artificial intelligence (AI), while ensuring a high level of protection of health, safety, fundamental rights enshrined in the EU Charter, including democracy, the rule of law and environmental protection, against the harmful effects of AI systems in the Union and supporting innovation.
Scope	The AI Act applies to AI systems being placed on the market or being put into service, or general-purpose AI models being placed on the market, in the EU or European Economic Area (EEA), regardless of whether the providers are established or located in the EU or EEA, or a third country. However, the regulation does not apply to AI systems or AI models, including their output, specifically developed and put into service for the sole purpose of scientific research and development (Art. 2(6)).
Relevance to PANDORA	The AI Act will not be applicable to PANDORA’s activities, given that the latter fall under the research exemption introduced in its Art. 2(6). However, the requirements set by the AI Act must be taken into account in order to create marketable and future-proof AI technology.

¹ ‘Provider’ means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body that develops an AI system or a general-purpose AI model or that has an AI system or a general-purpose AI model developed and places it on the market or puts the AI system into service under its own name or trademark, whether for payment or free of charge (AI Act, Art 3 (3)).

² Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act), PE/24/2024/REV/1. OJ L, 2024/1689, 12.7.2024.

³ This transitional period between the official entry of a law into force and its full implementation or enforcement aims to allow governments, businesses, and other affected parties time to prepare and comply with new rules.

	<p>In terms of the risk classification of the AI components of PANDORA, AI systems that ensure the reliability, accuracy, and safety of data pipelines for critical applications (like those in manufacturing and energy) may indirectly contribute to or support high-risk applications. Moreover, AI systems that interact with physical machinery or manage processes with potential safety implications (e.g., robotics, automation) align with high-risk use cases in the industrial sector.</p> <p>Regarding the interpretation of Art. 6 of the Act, further guidance by the Commission is expected by no longer than February 2026, including guidelines specifying its practical implementation together with a comprehensive list of practical examples of use cases of AI systems that are high-risk and not high-risk. It is important also to note that, at any case, the AI Act strongly promotes voluntary compliance with high-risk AI legal requirements.</p>
<p>Key practical implications</p>	<p>The following non-exhaustive list of requirements should be considered by the developers of the project’s AI system(s) and/or components:</p> <p>Transparency requirement: End-users of AI systems must be informed -at the time of the first interaction with the system- that they are interacting with an AI system, in a manner that is clear and appropriate to the need, capacities, and expertise of the end-users.</p> <p>Labelling requirement: The output generated is machine-readable and detectable as artificially generated, at the level of the system or at the level of the model.</p> <p>AI literacy requirement: Ensure that the deployers dealing with the operations and use of the PANDORA framework have the means, skills, knowledge and understanding to make an informed use of the AI systems and are aware of the opportunities and risks of AI, while also adopt technical and organisational measures to make sure that affected persons can access the knowledge necessary to understand how AI-supported decisions will have an impact on them.</p> <p>Requirements in relation to high-risk AI systems⁴:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk management: Establishment of a continuous and iterative risk management system involving the identification and evaluation of reasonably foreseeable risks to health, safety or fundamental rights, as arising from both intended use and reasonably foreseeable misuse, including the provision of appropriate measure to elimination or reduce said risks (Art. 9). • Data Governance: Ensure datasets for training, testing and validation of machine learning models meet are relevant, representative and -to the possible extent- free of errors); document design choices, data collection processes and origin, data preparation processes (i.e., annotation, labelling, cleaning, updating, enrichment and aggregation); clarify the assumptions about what the data measures and represents; assess the dataset’s availability, quantity and suitability; detect, prevent and mitigate possible biases; identify of relevant data gaps or shortcomings that prevent compliance with the overall requirements of the regulation, while having in mind the intended purpose of the system and the particular characteristics of the setting within which it will be used (Art 10). • Technical documentation: Maintain comprehensive documentation for auditability, allowing authorities to trace and review AI decisions. This includes general description of the AI system (e.g., its intended purpose, how the AI system interacts with hardware or software -including with other AI systems, the description of the hardware on which the AI system is intended to run, the instructions for use for the deployer), as well as a detailed description of the elements of the AI system and of the process for its development (Art. 11, Annex IV). • Record-keeping: Incorporate logging capabilities that allow for the automatic recording of events over the lifetime of the system, ensuring traceability and

⁴ This list is not meant to be exhaustive but serves as an overview of the main topics that these requirements cover.

	<p>facilitating monitoring. Logs should capture events that could indicate risks, support post-market monitoring, and document system operation. (Art. 12)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency and provision of information to deployers: systems must be accompanied by clear, comprehensive instructions covering provider details, system capabilities, performance metrics, known risks, and any limitations. Art. 13 details the necessary content of the information that must be conveyed with such said instructions. • Human oversight: AI systems must be designed to enable effective human oversight throughout their use. Oversight measures should be proportionate to the system's risks, autonomy, and context. These measures can include built-in controls or processes implemented by the deployer. Human overseers should be capable of understanding the system's capabilities, detecting anomalies, avoiding over-reliance, and, if necessary, overriding or stopping the AI (Art. 14). • Accuracy, Robustness, and Cybersecurity: Maintain appropriate levels of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity throughout the system's lifecycle. Systems should be resilient to errors, faults, and external threats, with measures such as redundancy and fail-safe mechanisms. For systems that continue learning after deployment, safeguards must prevent biased outputs from affecting future operations. Cybersecurity measures should protect against attacks like data/model poisoning, model evasion, and other vulnerabilities. Accuracy and performance metrics must be documented and included in the system's user instructions (Art. 15).
Link	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj

In the context of EU legislative initiatives on AI governance, it is also important to mention the ongoing process for the adoption of the proposal for the AI Liability Directive⁵, which aims to adapt non-contractual civil liability rules to the specific challenges posed by AI. This directive seeks to ensure that individuals can effectively claim compensation for harm caused by AI systems, addressing gaps in existing liability frameworks. It will establish clear rules for AI-related damages, aimed at enhancing legal certainty and accountability in AI technologies.⁶

Cybersecurity

Cybersecurity is a critical domain of consideration for systems designed to enhance the autonomy, trustworthiness, and energy efficiency of processes in smart space ecosystems. Threats to AIoT systems can undermine their accuracy, robustness, and fairness, ultimately impacting their overall trustworthiness. Implementing robust cybersecurity measures is essential to protect AIoT systems from potential threats such as data breaches, malware attacks, and unauthorized access. By ensuring the security of these systems, organizations can maintain the integrity and reliability of their operations within smart space ecosystems. Relevant EU legislative efforts have strived to provide a harmonized EU approach to cybersecurity requirements for providers of digital products and services, aimed at ensuring a high level of protection for consumers and businesses across member states. By establishing clear guidelines and standards, these efforts seek to mitigate the risks posed by cyber threats and promote a secure environment for the development and deployment of AIoT systems in smart spaces.

⁵ Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on adapting non-contractual civil liability rules to artificial intelligence (AI Liability Directive) COM/2022/496 final.

⁶ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-legal-affairs-juri/file-ai-liability-directive>.

Table 3: Cybersecurity-related EU Regulations and Directives

Cybersecurity Act (EU) 2019/881 ⁷	
Status	In force and applicable since 27 June 2019. On 18 April 2023, the Commission proposed a targeted amendment to the EU Cybersecurity Act. The proposed amendment will enable the future adoption of European certification schemes for ‘managed security services’ covering areas such as incident response, penetration testing, security audits and consultancy. ⁸
Purpose	To ensure high level of cybersecurity, cyber resilience and trust within the EU, by laying down the objectives, tasks and organisational matters relating to ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and establishing governance and rules for certification of ICT products, ICT services, and ICT processes -avoiding thus the fragmentation of the internal market with regard to cybersecurity certification schemes.
Scope	Applies EU-wide to ICT products, processes, and services, without prejudice to competencies regarding activities concerning public security, defense, national security, and the activities of the State in areas of criminal law.
Relevance to PANDORA	The overall governance framework and establishment of cybersecurity certification schemes for the purpose of ensuring an adequate level of cybersecurity for ICT products, services, and processes must be considered by the PANDORA consortium, considering the cybersecurity risks pertinent to the data flows throughout the use-cases and the overall design of the architecture of the envisioned framework.
Key practical implications	Consider aligning with the requirements of an appropriate European cybersecurity certification scheme.
Link	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/881/oj
Proposal for a Cyber Resilience Act (EU) ⁹	
Status	Close to adoption. The text of the proposal was adopted by the Parliament in March 2024. The Council approved the text on 10 October 2024. The text still needs to be signed and published in the Official Journal before it can enter into force. ¹⁰
Purpose	To ensure a high level of cybersecurity of products with digital elements and their integrated remote data processing solutions. ¹¹ This Regulation aims to set the boundary conditions for the development of secure products with digital elements by ensuring that hardware and software products are placed on the market with fewer vulnerabilities and that manufacturers take security

⁷ Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act) PE/86/2018/REV/1, OJ L 151, 7.6.2019, p. 15–69.

⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52023PC0208>.

⁹ Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020, COM/2022/454 final;

¹⁰ The act will be signed by the presidents of the Council and of the European Parliament, and will be published in the EU's official journal in the coming weeks. The new regulation will enter into force twenty days after this publication and will apply 36 months after its entry into force with some provisions to apply at an earlier stage. More information available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-europe-fit-for-the-digital-age/file-european-cyber-resilience-act>.

¹¹ ‘Product with digital elements’ means a software or hardware product and its remote data processing solutions, including software or hardware components being placed on the market separately; ‘Remote data processing’ means data processing at a distance for which the software is designed and developed by the manufacturer, or under the responsibility of the manufacturer, and the absence of which would prevent the product with digital elements from performing one of its functions;

	seriously throughout a product’s lifecycle. It also aims to create conditions allowing users to take cybersecurity into account when selecting and using products with digital elements, for example by improving transparency with regard to the support period for products with digital elements made available on the market.
Scope	It will apply to products with digital elements made available on the market, the intended purpose or reasonably foreseeable use of which includes a direct or indirect logical or physical data connection to a device or network.
Relevance to PANDORA	<p>The Cyber Resilience Act has not been yet applied and, even upon its adoption, the non-commercial ICT products with digital elements may be exempt (such as free and open-source software). Therefore, it does not apply to PANDORA and any evaluation of its relevance should be informed by the latest version of the Act’s text, upon its official publication.</p> <p>However, cybersecurity requirements provisioned in the Act must be taken into account in order to create marketable and future-proof technologies, considering that the components of the envisioned solution fall within the definition of “products with digital elements”.</p>
Key practical implications	Analyse cybersecurity risks and implement cybersecurity requirements, as provisioned within Art. 13 and Annex I of the proposal.
Link	https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/PE-100-2023-REV-1/en/pdf
NIS 2 Directive (EU) 2022/2555¹²	
Status	<p>In force since 16 January 2023</p> <p>The NIS2 Directive replaced the NIS Directive (EU) 2016/1148.</p> <p>Since 18 October 2024, all Member States must apply the measures necessary to comply with the NIS2 cybersecurity rules.</p>
Purpose	To enhance the cybersecurity of network and information systems across the European Union. It aims to establish a high common level of cybersecurity for entities operating in critical and important sectors
Scope	Applies to essential and important entities in critical sectors such as energy, transport, healthcare, finance, digital infrastructure, and public administration. It also includes digital service providers and covers entities operating within the EU.
Relevance to PANDORA	Although the directive is not applicable to the conduction of the research activities of the project, its provisions should be taken into account in the context of the design and development of the envisioned solution, given that it involves AIoT systems in smart space ecosystems, which fall under critical sectors like digital infrastructure and manufacturing.
Key practical implications	<p>Ensuring cybersecurity for data handling and AI model deployment that aligns with NIS 2 requirements for securing network and information systems, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • implementing appropriate cybersecurity risk management measures for AIoT systems. • establishing procedures for reporting significant cybersecurity incidents. • ensuring compliance with cybersecurity standards and cooperate with national authorities. • enhancing system resilience to cyber threats, safeguarding the trustworthiness and operational efficiency of AIoT processes.
Link	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02022L2555-20221227

¹² Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive).

Other examined regulations and directives

In addition to the above, the following EU Regulations and Directives are hereby enlisted and meant to be considered during the implementation of the action:

- The **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679**: The GDPR aims to protect the fundamental data protection rights and freedoms of natural persons residing within the EU and European Economic Area (EEA), as well as to establish a harmonized data protection framework across all EU and EEA member states, facilitating the free flow of personal data in these countries. It applies to the processing of personal data, defined broadly as any operation or set of operations performed on data relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. The GDPR shall apply to the project only if and when data structures used through its research may contain information that can lead to the identification of an end-user (e.g., IP, login info, devices serial number). However, and having considered the definition of the PANDORA use-cases' scenarios' design, no such cases have been identified to date. The GDPR may also be relevant for the collection of personal information in the case of workshop or other stakeholder engagement activity. It is noted that in such cases, relevant national regulations that have transposed the GDPR in the countries of relevance must be examined in terms of potential derogations that introduce stricter data protection provisions. To the extent that the regulation is applicable, the project as a whole should respect its principles and adopt appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure data protection and security.
- **ePrivacy Directive (2002/58/EC)** and the **proposal for an ePrivacy Regulation**¹³: The ePrivacy Directive aims to ensure the protection of privacy and personal data in electronic communications and to regulate issues such as confidentiality, data security, and spam. Insofar the project's AIoT-enabled datasets do not include personal data transmitted through electronic communications, the directive does not apply. The ePrivacy Regulation will update and strengthen privacy protections for electronic communications, harmonizing rules across the EU and addressing advancements in technology, such as IoT and AI. The proposal will impact how the project handles communication data in AIoT systems, particularly in ensuring privacy for data transmitted through smart space ecosystems. Although the same as above stands with regards to the applicability of the proposed regulation, it is important to monitor its development, particularly concerning the evolving privacy and security requirements for IoT communications.
- The **Data Governance Act (EU) 2022/868**¹⁴ and the **Data Act (EU) 2023/2854**¹⁵: The Data Governance Act aims to establish a framework for data sharing and governance within the EU, promoting the reuse of public sector data and enabling data sharing across sectors. The Data Act – which will become applicable in September 2025- aims to establish rules for fair data access, use, and sharing across the EU. It will apply to all raw and pre-processed data generated from the use of a connected product or a related service that is readily available to the data holder – i.e., the company that makes the connected product or that provides a related service. The Data Act complements the Data Governance Act, clarifying who can create value from data and under which conditions. It provisions that connected products will have to be designed and manufactured in a way that empowers users (businesses or consumers) to easily and securely access, use and share the generated

¹³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52017PC0010>

¹⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/868/oj>

¹⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32023R2854&qid=1730717911993>

data, including provisions regarding minimum requirements to facilitate interoperability. In the context of the transition of the manufacturing landscape towards more cyber and digital infrastructure, including the integration technologies such as AIoT, the exchange of data is expected to grow massively. Training and improving AI models may benefit from the creation of sector-specific data spaces and frameworks enabling access to high-quality public sector data and ensuring secure and transparent data sharing, as well as from data altruism practices that encourage voluntary data sharing. Thus, monitoring the implementation of these regulations and their impact in the delivery of datasets for AIoT model training in manufacturing settings is considered of relevance to PANDORA.

5.2.2 Guidelines and Recommendations

Within the past decade, the growing global discourse on AI ethics and governance has led numerous organisations and regulatory bodies to issue guidelines and recommendations prescribing ethical principles and subsequent requirements for the design, deployment, and use of AI systems. The most prominent EU ethics framework for trustworthy AI development and deployment has been laid down by the AI ethics guidelines developed by the European Commission's (EC) High Level Expert Group in 2019¹⁶. The guidelines provided seven key ethical requirements for Trustworthy AI, derived from the fundamental ethical principles of respect for autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness, and explicability, as follows:

- **Human agency and oversight:** AI systems should empower human beings, allowing them to make informed decisions and fostering their fundamental rights. At the same time, proper oversight mechanisms need to be ensured, which can be achieved through human-in-the-loop, human-on-the-loop, and human-in-command approaches.
- **Technical Robustness and safety:** AI systems need to be resilient to attack and secure. They need to be safe, ensuring a fallback plan in case something goes wrong, as well as being accurate, reliable, and reproducible. That is the only way to ensure that also unintentional harm can be minimized and prevented.
- **Privacy and data governance:** besides ensuring full respect for privacy and data protection, adequate data governance mechanisms must also be ensured, taking into account the quality and integrity of the data, and ensuring legitimised access to data.
- **Transparency:** the data, system and AI business models should be transparent. Traceability mechanisms can help achieve this. Moreover, AI systems and their decisions should be explained in a manner adapted to the stakeholder concerned. Humans need to be aware that they are interacting with an AI system and must be informed of the system's capabilities and limitations.
- **Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness:** unfair bias must be avoided, as it could have multiple negative implications, from the marginalisation of vulnerable groups to the exacerbation of prejudice and discrimination. Fostering diversity, AI systems should be accessible to all, regardless of any disability, and involve relevant stakeholders throughout their entire life circle.
- **Societal and environmental well-being:** AI systems should benefit all human beings, including future generations. It must hence be ensured that they are sustainable and environmentally friendly. Moreover, they should take into account the environment, including other living beings, and their social and societal impact should be carefully considered.

¹⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

- **Accountability:** Mechanisms should be put in place to ensure responsibility and accountability for AI systems and their outcomes. Auditability, which enables the assessment of algorithms, data and design processes, plays a key role therein, especially in critical applications. Moreover, adequate accessible redress should be ensured.

Other guidelines and recommendations (EU or international) deemed of relevance in the context of PANDORA are hereby enlisted:

- The IEEE’s “Ethically Aligned Design: A Vision for Prioritizing Human Wellbeing with Autonomous and Intelligent Systems” (EAD First Edition), from 2019.
- The OECD’s “Recommendation on Artificial Intelligence (OECD AI Principles), as updated in May 2024.
- The ENISA’s Multilayer Framework for Good Cybersecurity Practices for AI, from 2023
- The NIST’s Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework (AI RMF 1.0), released in January 2023.
- The European Data Protection Supervisor’s “Generative AI and the EUDPR: First EDPS Orientations for Ensuring Data Protection Compliance When Using Generative AI Systems”, from 03 June 2024.

5.2.3 Standards

Following the enforcement of the AI Act, AI systems will be subject to significant standardisation efforts or "common specifications" when "harmonised standards" cannot be adopted (AI Act, Art. 41). These standards will cover essential requirements such as transparency, robustness, and other performance metrics, with the EC promoting the development of shared benchmarks (AI Act, Rec. 74 and Art. 15(2)). Compliance with these harmonised standards or common specifications will provide a presumption of conformity with the AI Act’s legal requirements (AI Act, Art. 40 and 41). This initiative is aligned with international standardisation efforts, fostering global cooperation while ensuring that EU values are upheld. Several key organisations are leading the charge in developing AI standards. CEN-CENELEC, through its dedicated Focus Group on Artificial Intelligence, is working to harmonize AI standards that align with the ethical and regulatory requirements outlined in the EU AI Act. The ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 subcommittee focuses on AI at the international level, while the IEEE 7000 series provide critical guidelines addressing ethical concerns in technology design, together informing European standardisation efforts and contributing foundational guidelines that influence the development of standards aimed at ensuring trustworthy and ethically sound AI systems. Such standards, as well as ones related to cybersecurity, altogether considered of relevance to PANDORA, are outlined in the following table.

Table 4: List of standards relevant to PANDORA:

Number/Code	Title	Status	Link
ISO/IEC 27001:2022	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Information security management systems — Requirements	Published	https://www.iso.org/standard/27001
ISO/IEC 27701:2019	Security techniques — Extension to ISO/IEC 27001 and ISO/IEC 27002 for privacy information management — Requirements and guidelines	Published	https://www.iso.org/standard/71670.html

ISO/IEC TR 24368:2022	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of ethical and societal concerns	Published	https://www.iso.org/standard/78507.html
ISO/IEC 22989:2022	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Artificial intelligence concepts and terminology	Published	https://www.iso.org/standard/74296.html
ISO/IEC 15408-1:2022	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Evaluation criteria for IT security	Published	https://www.iso.org/standard/72891.html
ISO/IEC 23894:2023	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Guidance on risk management	Published	https://www.iso.org/standard/77304.html
ISO/IEC 42001:2023	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Management system	Published	https://www.iso.org/standard/81230.html
ISO/IEC FDIS 42005	Information technology — Artificial intelligence — AI system impact assessment	Under development	https://www.iso.org/standard/44545.html#lifecycle
IEEE 7000-2021	IEEE Standard Model Process for Addressing Ethical Concerns during System Design	Published	https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/7000/6781/
IEEE 7001-2021	IEEE Standard for Transparency of Autonomous Systems	Published	https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/7001/6929/
IEEE 7007-2021	IEEE Ontological Standard for Ethically Driven Robotics and Automation Systems	Published	https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/7007/7070/
IEEE P7100	Standard for Measurement of Environmental Impacts of Artificial Intelligence Systems	Published	https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/7100/11671/

5.3 Compliance and risk assessment

Within the EU, several initiatives have been undertaken to assess and manage the impacts of AI on fundamental rights and societal interests. While a unified definition of AI impact assessments is still evolving, key efforts focusing on ethical considerations, regulatory compliance, and risk management include the following:

Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI)¹⁷: A practical tool to facilitate a self-assessment regarding compliance with the seven requirements of the EC’s Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI at all stages of the design and development of AI systems. ALTAI encompasses detailed questions and considerations, facilitating a systematic evaluation process. Its methodology encourages a multi-stakeholder approach, ensuring that diverse perspectives are integrated into the assessment process. Implementing the ALTAI involves iterative self-assessment, and continuous improvement. In that sense, organizations are encouraged to actively engage in a process of understanding the questions posed, reflecting on the implied risks, and trying to investigate how to best address them. They are also encouraged to tailor the list according to the

¹⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>

specific aspects of their AI applications, thus promoting more effective and ethically sound AI solutions.

ENISA’s Framework for good cybersecurity practices for AI: ENISA suggests adherence to established standards (e.g., ISO/IEC standards on information security) and promotes regular compliance assessments to verify that the AI system aligns with existing EU regulations on AI ethics and security, amongst other. The framework advises implementing processes for incident reporting and vulnerability management to assess and mitigate risks actively, ensuring resilience against emerging threats and vulnerabilities in AI systems.

5.4 Literature overview

While there is significant convergence within the global discourse on high-level AI ethics principles (as reflected upon the relevant guidelines), challenges persist in their practical application [FAH20], [RS20], [H20]. These principles, often contested and subject to multiple interpretations, risk being selectively applied to align with corporate incentives rather than ethical responsibilities leading to problems like relativism or ethics washing [Ma19]. Many raise concerns over the lack of context-specific ethical framework, as well as over the underrepresentation of the global south in the respective dialogue and stress that balancing global ethical frameworks with localized implementations is crucial to address diverse societal needs [JIV19].

The literature on implementation challenges frequently addresses the trade-off between transparency and performance, and namely the balance between explainability and accuracy. Simplifying models to enhance explainability often leads to a drop in performance, posing a significant challenge in contexts where both high accuracy and explainability are critical. Schoenherr et al. [SAM23] argue that the appropriate balance is context-dependent, especially in safety-critical domains where accuracy is particularly crucial, although it must not come at the cost of sufficient explainability for informed decision-making.

Moreover, the need for tailored explanations that are intuitive, meaningful, and relevant for end-users is stressed, considering that most current XAI methods are algorithm-centric and lack practical usability [LGM20]. Developers need detailed insights into the model's internal workings, while end-users benefit from simpler, trust-building explanations. In this direction, it is argued that effective and human-centered explainability should be contrastive, causal, and socially tailored to align with human reasoning preferences [AAE23], [Mb19].

The way that the concept of “trust” is being approached has also been contested, namely by criticizing an instrumental approach to trust which often treats trust as a means to promote AI adoption rather than as an intrinsic ethical value, leading to a more transactional relationship with AI, where trustworthiness is prioritized only insofar as it promotes AI's effectiveness, potentially overlooking deeper moral obligations or user autonomy [R23]. In differentiating between trust (a user's subjective confidence) and trustworthiness (the objective qualities of an AI system) in AI ethics, scholars suggest understanding trust in AI as a socio-technical phenomenon that extends beyond technology to encompass organizational and relational dynamics, and stress that ethical principles should be applied contextually rather than uniformly across AI applications [DD23]. While understanding user perspectives is essential, as trust develops based on user experiences and perceptions over time [SAM23], Reinhardt also suggests that formalized mechanisms of institutionalized distrust—such as audits and regulatory standards—may, in some cases, better safeguard ethical AI than solely focusing on building user trust [R23]. Campagner et al. [CAC23] advocates for complementary metrics to assess AI trustworthiness, highlighting factors such as source reliability, pragmatic utility, decision benefits, and robustness, which collectively contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of trust in AI systems. In this context, the gap between high-level ethical aspirations and actionable tools for AI design is also of relevance as it

underscores the need for interdisciplinary collaboration, which can bridge differences in terminology, methodologies, and priorities [BD23], [Ma19].

The collection of large datasets, particularly in AIoT systems, raises also concerns about unauthorized access and cyber threats, as AIoT devices, often operating on outdated systems, are vulnerable to attacks and unauthorized data access. To mitigate these risks, stronger authentication, data encryption, and secure communication protocols are recommended, alongside standardized security models to protect sensitive data and maintain trust in AIoT applications [K23]. Moreover, while inadequate protections increase the risk of security breaches, strong privacy measures like encryption and restricted access can limit data usability. Additionally, these protective methods often come at the cost of reduced model performance due to diminished data fidelity [SDL23]. Frameworks like ENISA's multi-layer framework and NIST's AI Risk Management Framework, offer valuable insights but require adaptation to address human-centered risks effectively [PPK24]. Ensuring the quality and integrity of datasets is foundational to building trust in AI systems, especially in the case of non-human-facing applications where human-centered values might not be explicitly prioritized [SDL23].

In terms of the EU legal framework on AI, Ebers et al. [EHR21] emphasize the need for clearer guidance on how different frameworks interact to avoid regulatory overlaps and inconsistencies, especially to prevent potential duplicative conformity assessments. Concerns also arise over the AI Act's reliance on self-assessment for most high-risk AI systems, with critics recommending mandatory external oversight for critical applications to ensure thorough evaluation and accountability. According to public consultation insights presented in a study by Renda et al. [RAF21], relevant stakeholders highlighted the need for clear definitions of "high-risk" AI, improved regulatory clarity, and a balanced regulatory burden, especially for SMEs. They urged for the implementation of cost-effective certification schemes and the development of quality management systems to support regulatory adherence without imposing excessive financial burdens on developers.

5.5 Survey-based requirements elicitation

Engaging consortium partners and, eventually, a broader array of stakeholders through a survey-based approach is essential to collect insights on legal and ethical considerations pertinent to the development and deployment of the project's AI-based framework. Survey-based requirements elicitation provides a structured method for understanding how consortium members interpret key regulatory and ethical requirements, as well as the specific challenges they anticipate in adhering to their provisions, offering critical insights into potential obstacles, such as ensuring model accuracy, enhancing explainability, and maintaining robust cybersecurity. This will help to better align the work of the project with evolving societal expectations and ethical standards, as well as to address new concerns about the broader impacts of AI as they arise. This process establishes a feedback loop, whereby continuous input from stakeholders can guide iterative improvements, facilitating context-aware adaptations and ensuring that the project remains ethically sound, legally compliant, and responsive to the expectations of an extended community.

5.6 Conclusions and recommendations

Given the preliminary identification of the normative framework relevant to PANDORA, the envisioned framework for optimizing the preparation and delivery of trustworthy datasets for AI models deployed in AIoT systems should be designed, developed, and implemented in compliance with the principles and standards established by the EC's High-Level Expert Group on AI's Ethics Guidelines. Security should be embedded by design, incorporating robust security mechanisms. Additionally, the framework should align with key requirements set by relevant

regulatory frameworks, including the EU AI Act and the Cyber Resilience Act, while GDPR compliance must be ensured insofar any personal data processing activity is involved. Moreover, ethics compliance and risk assessments must be conducted focusing on the seven requirements for trustworthy AI defined by AI HLEG (e.g., ALTAI) and considering also relevant approaches proposed by ENISA. The socio-technical context across various use-case scenarios should be carefully evaluated when assessing conformity with the applicable normative framework (e.g., during completion of ALTAI). Careful consideration must be given to the provision of human-centered explanations for the advanced or deployed models, considering the need for varying complexity levels adapted to different stakeholders' domain knowledge. Further, potential trade-offs between AI ethics requirements, such as transparency versus accuracy, must be identified and their resolution must be justified with close attention to the needs of specific domains like manufacturing and other critical sectors. It is also essential to gather insights on the perceptions and considerations regarding the ethical and legal requirements of relevance to the project, both internally (engaging consortium partners) and externally (interested stakeholders). Lastly, the framework should monitor the evolving regulatory landscape, especially forthcoming regarding the anticipated guidelines and recommendations related to the interpretation and implementation of the AI Act, to ensure continued compliance and relevance.

6. Conclusions

The Deliverable D2.1 – Project Setup, highlights the successful establishment of a foundational structure for the PANDORA project, particularly in advancing the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT), collectively termed AIoT. Through D2.1, the project has put specific essential elements, including technical standards, ethical guidelines, and legal frameworks, which position PANDORA to meet European Union (EU) regulations and encourage ethical and responsible AI use across a range of applications.

This deliverable plays a crucial role in fostering a multidisciplinary approach, bringing together consortium members with expertise across various fields. This collaborative foundation encourages research aimed at creating resilient, adaptable, and secure AIoT systems. The formation of the Scientific Board and the clear articulation of initial objectives ensure that ongoing research aligns with PANDORA's commitment to transparency, accountability, and AI applications, thus supporting the overall success of the project.

A significant emphasis of D2.1 is on legal compliance and alignment with EU ethical standards, particularly with regard to data privacy, cybersecurity, and the emerging EU AI regulatory framework. By adhering to GDPR, the AI Act, and other regulatory requirements, PANDORA ensures that its AIoT solutions meet high standards of data security and responsible AI. This alignment not only positions PANDORA as a leader in ethical AI development but also addresses critical challenges of deploying high-risk AI applications in industries where safety and trustworthiness are paramount.

In summary, Deliverable D2.1 establishes a robust and adaptable framework that supports PANDORA's ambitious goals of creating trustworthy and sustainable AIoT technologies. By focusing on compliance, ethical standards, and technological guidelines, it provides the necessary structure for the successful execution of the project's objectives across all Work Packages, laying a strong foundation for innovation and impact within AIoT ecosystems.

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Annex A

Table 5: Strategies and project related

Strategies	Project related to this task
1	<p>Scheduling continuous operators for IoT edge analytics with time constraints doi: 10.1109/SMARTCOMP55677.2022.00026</p> <p>Continual Transformers: Redundancy-Free Attention for Online Inference doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2201.06268</p> <p>Continual 3D Convolutional Neural Networks for Real-time Processing of Videos doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2106.00050</p> <p>Continual Spatio-Temporal Graph Convolutional Networks doi: 10.1016/j.patcog.2023.109528</p> <p>Receptive-field based Segmentation for Distributed CNN Inference Acceleration in Collaborative Edge Computing doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2207.11293</p> <p>Distributed Deep Learning Inference Acceleration using Seamless Collaboration in Edge Computing doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2207.11294</p> <p>Collaborative Edge Computing for Distributed CNN Inference Acceleration using Receptive field-based Segmentation doi: 10.1016/j.comnet.2022.109150</p> <p>Graph Reinforcement Learning-based CNN Inference Offloading in Dynamic Edge Computing doi: 10.1109/GLOBECOM48099.2022.10001067</p> <p>Open Traffic Data for Mobility-as-a-Service Applications—Architecture and Challenges doi: 10.1201/9781003337232-31</p> <p>Engineering Resource-Efficient Data Management for Smart Cities with Apache Kafka doi: 10.3390/fi15020043</p> <p>SmartSPEC: A framework to generate customizable, semantics-based smart space datasets doi: 10.1016/j.pmcj.2023.101809</p> <p>PlanIoT: a framework for adaptive data flow management in IoT-enhanced spaces doi: 10.1109/SEAMS59076.2023.00029</p> <p>AI Defenders: Machine Learning Driven Anomaly Detection in Critical Infrastructures</p> <p>Securing Machine-to-Machine Communication in the Nuclear Domain with OPC UA</p> <p>Optimizing the fuel management in a VVER-1000 reactor using an artificial neural network doi:10.1016/j.anucene.2011.12.010</p> <p>Optimization of Training Dataset Size for Predicting Homogenized Macroscopic Cross-Sections using Deep Neural Network</p> <p>Radiation Dosimetry, Artificial Intelligence and Digital Twins: Old Dog, New Tricks doi: 10.1053/J.SEMNUCLMED.2022.10.007</p> <p>Image Sorting of Nuclear Reactions Recorded on CR-39 Nuclear Track Detector Using Deep Learning doi: 10.1016/J.RADMEAS.2022.106706</p> <p>Simutack - An Attack Simulation Framework for Connected and Autonomous Vehicles</p> <p>Attack data generation framework for autonomous vehicle sensors</p> <p>Generative AI and Cognitive Computing-Driven Intrusion Detection System in Industrial CPS doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13254989</p> <p>Fledge: Benchmarking federated machine learning applications in edge computing systems doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2306.05172</p> <p>Energy vs Privacy: Estimating the Ecological Impact of Federated Learning doi: 10.1145/3575813.3597344</p> <p>A survey on efficient federated learning methods for foundation model training doi: arXiv:2401.04472</p> <p>How Can We Train Deep Learning Models Across Clouds and Continents? An Experimental Study doi: arXiv:2306.03163</p>

	<p>Few-shot learning for defect detection in manufacturing doi: 10.1080/00207543.2024.2316279</p> <p>Robust Anomaly Map Assisted Multiple Defect Detection with Supervised Classification Techniques doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2023.10.1144</p> <p>Predicting Operators' Fatigue in a Human in the Artificial Intelligence Loop for Defect Detection in Manufacturing doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2023.10.1157</p> <p>Synthetic Data Augmentation Using GAN For Improved Automated Visual Inspection doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2023.10.817</p> <p>Robust Anomaly Map Assisted Multiple Defect Detection with Supervised Classification Techniques doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2023.10.1144</p> <p>Towards A Comprehensive Visual Quality Inspection For Industry 4.0 doi: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2022.09.486</p> <p>Active Learning for Automated Visual Inspection of Manufactured Products doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2109.02469</p> <p>Streaming Machine Learning and Online Active Learning for Automated Visual Inspection doi: arXiv.2110.09396</p> <p>PHOENIX – A European Cyber Resilience Framework With Artificial Intelligence-Assisted Orchestration Automation for Business Continuity, Incident Response & Information Exchange doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2307.06932</p> <p>Papadaki, A.; Pateraki, M. 6D Object Localization in Car-Assembly Industrial Environment. J. Imaging 2023, 9, 72. https://doi.org/10.3390/jimaging9030072</p> <p>Crane Spreader Pose Estimation from a Single View. 10.5220/0011788800003417</p> <p>A lightweight storage framework for edge computing infrastructures/EdgePersist doi: 10.1016/j.simpa.2023.100549</p> <p>Dynamic Adaptability in Human-Robot Collaboration for Industrial Assembly: A Behaviour Tree Based Task Execution PlanEMQx: https://github.com/satrai-lab/planemqx</p> <p>SmartSPEC: https://github.com/andrewgchio/SmartSPEC</p>
<p>2</p>	<p>Covert timing channel attack on OPC UA-based industrial control systems</p> <p>AI Defenders: Machine Learning Driven Anomaly Detection in Critical Infrastructures</p> <p>Consideration of Artificial Intelligence for Cybersecurity Aspects of I&C</p> <p>Multi-objective optimization method for nuclear reactor radiation shielding design based on PSO algorithm doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2021.108404</p> <p>Machine Learning in Industrial X-Ray Computed Tomography – a Review. doi: 10.1016/J.CIRPJ.2024.05.004</p> <p>Papadaki, A.; Pateraki, M. 6D Object Localization in Car-Assembly Industrial Environment. J. Imaging 2023, 9, 72. https://doi.org/10.3390/jimaging9030072</p> <p>Crane Spreader Pose Estimation from a Single View. 10.5220/0011788800003417</p> <p>A lightweight storage framework for edge computing infrastructures/EdgePersist doi: 10.1016/j.simpa.2023.100549</p> <p>Dynamic Adaptability in Human-Robot Collaboration for Industrial Assembly: A Behaviour Tree Based Task Execution</p>

<p>3</p>	<p>Erebus: explaining the outputs of data streaming queries. In Very Large Data Base doi: 10.14778/3565816.3565825 A meta-level analysis of online anomaly detectors doi:10.1007/s00778-022-00773-x PROTEUS: Predictive Explanation of Anomalies doi:10.1109/ICDE51399.2021.00185 Towards a topological-geometrical theory of group equivariant non-expansive operators for data analysis and machine learning DOI: 10.48550/arXiv.1812.11832 Ensuring trustworthy AI for sensitive infrastructure using Knowledge Representation Using Knowledge Representation to achieve Reliable and trustworthy AI in Sensitive Infrastructure Machine Learning in Industrial X-Ray Computed Tomography – a Review. doi: 10.1016/J.CIRPJ.2024.05.004 Digital twins-enabled zero-touch network: A smart contract and explainable AI integrated cybersecurity framework doi: 10.1016/j.future.2024.02.015 On the finite representation of linear group equivariant operators via permutant measures doi: 10.1007/s10472-022-09830-1 A topological model for partial equivariance in deep learning and data analysis doi: 10.3389/frai.2023.1272619 Generalized Permutants and Graph GENEOS doi: https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2206.14798</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>C4IoT: https://zenodo.org/records/4686782 The Application of Machine Learning Techniques in Prediction of Quality of Life Features for Cancer Patients doi: 10.2298/CSIS220227061S Model-based integrity monitoring of Industrial Automation and Control Systems doi: 10.18420/inf2022_132</p>
<p>5</p>	<p>Open Traffic Data for Mobility-as-a-Service Applications–Architecture and Challenges doi: 10.1201/9781003337232-31 Engineering Resource-Efficient Data Management for Smart Cities with Apache Kafka doi: 10.3390/fi15020043 Designing Trustworthy Monitoring Systems - Forensic Readiness for Safety and Security doi:10.1109/ICRMS.2018.00038 Machine Learning in Neutron Scattering Data Analysis doi: 10.1016/J.JRRAS.2024.100870 A Virtual Machine Management Platform in Computer Science Education. 2024 3rd International Conference on Computer Engineering, Technologies and Applications.</p>
<p>6</p>	<p>AI Defenders: Machine Learning Driven Anomaly Detection in Critical Infrastructures Cyber Security Risk Analysis and Technical Defense Architecture Research of ICS in Nuclear Power Plant Construction Stage Optimizing the fuel management in a VVER-1000 reactor using an artificial neural network doi:10.1016/j.anucene.2011.12.010 Application of artificial neural network for assembly homogenized equivalence parameter generation doi: 10.1016/j.pnucene.2024.105285 Feasibility study on application of an artificial neural network for automatic design of a reactor core at the Kyoto University Critical Assembly doi: 10.1016/j.pnucene.2019.103183 Multi-objective optimization method for nuclear reactor radiation shielding design based on PSO algorithm doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2021.108404</p>

	<p>Machine Learning in Neutron Scattering Data Analysis doi: 10.1016/J.JRRAS.2024.100870 A Virtual Machine Management Platform in Computer Science Education. 2024 3rd International Conference on Computer Engineering, Technologies and Applications.</p>
<p>7</p>	<p>C4IIoT: https://zenodo.org/records/4686782 I-BiDaaS: https://zenodo.org/records/4264473 I-BiDaaS: https://zenodo.org/records/4321371 A meta-level analysis of online anomaly detectors doi:10.1007/s00778-022-00773-x Scheduling continuous operators for IoT edge analytics with time constraints doi: 10.1109/SMARTCOMP55677.2022.00026 The Role of Federated Learning in Processing Cancer Patients' Data doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-42194-5_4 The Application of Machine Learning Techniques in Prediction of Quality of Life Features for Cancer Patients doi: 10.2298/CSIS220227061S Deep Learning Anomaly Detection for Cellular IoT With Applications in Smart Logistics DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3072916 BACS: A comprehensive tool for deep learning-based anomaly detection in edge-fog-cloud systems DOI: 10.23919/EUSIPCO55093.2022.9909721 Edge Machine Learning in 3GPP NB-IoT: Architecture, Applications and Demonstration DOI: 10.23919/EUSIPCO55093.2022.9909793 A One-Shot Framework for Distributed Clustered Learning in Heterogeneous Environments doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2209.10866 Covert timing channel attack on OPC UA-based industrial control systems A Virtual Machine Management Platform in Computer Science Education. 2024 3rd International Conference on Computer Engineering, Technologies and Applications. Digital twins-enabled zero-touch network: A smart contract and explainable AI integrated cybersecurity framework doi: 10.1016/j.future.2024.02.015 SYNAPSE - An Integrated Cybersecurity Risk & Resilience Management Platform, With Holistic Situational Awareness, Incident Response & Preparedness Capabilities doi: 10.1145/3664476.3669924 Federated Learning and AI Regulation in the European Union: Who is Responsible?—An Interdisciplinary Analysis. doi: https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2407.08105 A survey on efficient federated learning methods for foundation model training doi: arXiv:2401.04472 FlatPack: flexible temporal planning with verification and controller synthesis. SoK: Membership Inference is Harder Than Previously Thought doi: https://doi.org/10.56553/popets-2023-0082 Been here already? Detecting Synchronized Browsers in the Wild doi: https://doi.org/10.1109/EuroSP57164.2023.00058 Continuous Security Assurance of Modern Supply-Chain Ecosystems with Application in Autonomous Driving doi: https://doi.org/10.1109/CSR57506.2023.10224971 Creating a Security Enforcement Environment for a Vehicular Platform doi: http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/CSCN60443.2023.10453176 Providing Security Assurance & Hardening for Open Source Software/Hardware: The SecOPERA approach doi:</p>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/CAMAD59638.2023.10478410>
 The Million Dollar Handshake: Secure and Attested Communications in the Cloud | doi: 10.1109/CLOUD49709.2020.00022
 Andromeda: Enabling Secure Enclaves for the Android Ecosystem | doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-91356-4_11
 Network Intrusion Detection in Encrypted Traffic | doi: 10.1109/DSC54232.2022.9888942
 BACS software C4IIoT: <https://zenodo.org/records/6557696>
 I-BiDaaS, distributed ADMM, COMPSs/dislib:
https://github.com/ibidaas/knowledge_repository/tree/master/tools_technologies/sources/batch_processing/unspmf
 FedL software (non-uniform sampling for FL, Flower framework) MARVEL: <https://github.com/nmilosev/fedl>
 Federated learning software (FL with Moreau envelopes, Flower framework) Marvel/TARDIS:
https://github.com/angelili/projekat_DDU/tree/main
 Pybiscus, a framework for federated learning: <https://github.com/ThalesGroup/pybiscus>

8

Receptive-field based Segmentation for Distributed CNN Inference Acceleration in Collaborative Edge Computing | doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2207.11293

Distributed Deep Learning Inference Acceleration using Seamless Collaboration in Edge Computing | doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2207.11294

Collaborative Edge Computing for Distributed CNN Inference Acceleration using Receptive field-based Segmentation | doi: 10.1016/j.comnet.2022.109150

Graph Reinforcement Learning-based CNN Inference Offloading in Dynamic Edge Computing | doi: 10.1109/GLOBECOM48099.2022.10001067

Optimization of Training Dataset Size for Predicting Homogenized Macroscopic Cross-Sections using Deep Neural Network Federated Learning-based Personalized Recommendation Systems: An Overview on Security and Privacy Challenges | doi: 10.1109/TCE.2023.3318754

SYNAPSE - An Integrated Cybersecurity Risk & Resilience Management Platform, With Holistic Situational Awareness, Incident Response & Preparedness Capabilities | doi: 10.1145/3664476.3669924

Federated Learning and AI Regulation in the European Union: Who is Responsible?—An Interdisciplinary Analysis. | doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2407.08105>

A survey on efficient federated learning methods for foundation model training | doi: arXiv:2401.04472

Few-shot learning for defect detection in manufacturing | doi: 10.1080/00207543.2024.2316279

Robust Anomaly Map Assisted Multiple Defect Detection with Supervised Classification Techniques | doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2023.10.1144

Predicting Operators' Fatigue in a Human in the Artificial Intelligence Loop for Defect Detection in Manufacturing | doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2023.10.1157

Synthetic Data Augmentation Using GAN For Improved Automated Visual Inspection | doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2023.10.817

Robust Anomaly Map Assisted Multiple Defect Detection with Supervised Classification Techniques | doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2023.10.1144

Towards A Comprehensive Visual Quality Inspection For Industry 4.0 | doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2022.09.486>

Active Learning for Automated Visual Inspection of Manufactured Products | doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2109.02469

Streaming Machine Learning and Online Active Learning for Automated Visual Inspection | doi: arXiv.2110.09396

I-BiDaaS, distributed ADMM, COMPSs/dislib:
https://github.com/ibidaas/knowledge_repository/tree/master/tools_technologies/sources/batch_processing/unspmf

FedL software (non-uniform sampling for FL, Flower framework) MARVEL: <https://github.com/nmilosev/fedl>

Federated learning software (FL with Moreau envelopes, Flower framework) Marvel/TARDIS:
https://github.com/angelili/projekat_DDU/tree/main

Pybiscus, a framework for federated learning: <https://github.com/ThalesGroup/pybiscus>

9

Erebus: explaining the outputs of data streaming queries. In Very Large Data Base | doi: 10.14778/3565816.3565825
 A meta-level analysis of online anomaly detectors | doi:10.1007/s00778-022-00773-x
 PROTEUS: Predictive Explanation of Anomalies | doi:10.1109/ICDE51399.2021.00185
 Scheduling continuous operators for IoT edge analytics with time constraints | doi: 10.1109/SMARTCOMP55677.2022.00026
 Continual Transformers: Redundancy-Free Attention for Online Inference | doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2201.06268
 Graph Reinforcement Learning-based CNN Inference Offloading in Dynamic Edge Computing | doi: 10.1109/GLOBECOM48099.2022.10001067
 Towards a topological-geometrical theory of group equivariant non-expansive operators for data analysis and machine learning | DOI: 10.48550/arXiv.1812.11832
 The Application of Machine Learning Techniques in Prediction of Quality of Life Features for Cancer Patients | doi: 10.2298/CSIS220227061S
 Deep Learning Anomaly Detection for Cellular IoT With Applications in Smart Logistics | DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3072916
 BACS: A comprehensive tool for deep learning-based anomaly detection in edge-fog-cloud systems | DOI: 10.23919/EUSIPCO55093.2022.9909721
 Ensuring trustworthy AI for sensitive infrastructure using Knowledge Representation
 Using Knowledge Representation to achieve Reliable and trustworthy AI in Sensitive Infrastructure
 Designing Trustworthy Monitoring Systems - Forensic Readiness for Safety and Security | doi:10.1109/ICRMS.2018.00038
 Machine Learning Methods as a Tool to Analyse Incomplete or Irregularly Sampled Radon Time Series Data | doi: 10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2018.02.233
 Digital twins-enabled zero-touch network: A smart contract and explainable AI integrated cybersecurity framework | doi: 10.1016/j.future.2024.02.015
 Few-shot learning for defect detection in manufacturing | doi: 10.1080/00207543.2024.2316279
 On the finite representation of linear group equivariant operators via permutant measures | doi: 10.1007/s10472-022-09830-1
 A topological model for partial equivariance in deep learning and data analysis | doi: 10.3389/frai.2023.1272619
 Generalized Permutants and Graph GENEOS | doi: https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2206.14798
 BACS software C4IIoT: https://zenodo.org/records/6557696

<p>10</p>	<p>Scheduling continuous operators for IoT edge analytics with time constraints doi: 10.1109/SMARTCOMP55677.2022.00026 Continual Transformers: Redundancy-Free Attention for Online Inference doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2201.06268 Continual 3D Convolutional Neural Networks for Real-time Processing of Videos doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2106.00050 Continual Spatio-Temporal Graph Convolutional Networks doi: 10.1016/j.patcog.2023.109528 Receptive-field based Segmentation for Distributed CNN Inference Acceleration in Collaborative Edge Computing doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2207.11293 Distributed Deep Learning Inference Acceleration using Seamless Collaboration in Edge Computing doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2207.11294 Collaborative Edge Computing for Distributed CNN Inference Acceleration using Receptive field-based Segmentation doi: 10.1016/j.comnet.2022.109150 Graph Reinforcement Learning-based CNN Inference Offloading in Dynamic Edge Computing doi: 10.1109/GLOBECOM48099.2022.10001067 PlanIoT: a framework for adaptive data flow management in IoT-enhanced spaces doi: 10.1109/SEAMS59076.2023.00029 Securing Machine-to-Machine Communication in the Nuclear Domain with OPC UA Generative AI and Cognitive Computing-Driven Intrusion Detection System in Industrial CPS doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13254989 PlanEMQx: https://github.com/satrai-lab/planemqx</p>
<p>11</p>	<p>Optimizing the fuel management in a VVER-1000 reactor using an artificial neural network doi:10.1016/j.anucene.2011.12.010 Optimization of Training Dataset Size for Predicting Homogenized Macroscopic Cross-Sections using Deep Neural Network Radiation Dosimetry, Artificial Intelligence and Digital Twins: Old Dog, New Tricks doi: 10.1053/J.SEMNUCLMED.2022.10.007 Image Sorting of Nuclear Reactions Recorded on CR-39 Nuclear Track Detector Using Deep Learning doi: 10.1016/J.RADMEAS.2022.106706 Generative AI and Cognitive Computing-Driven Intrusion Detection System in Industrial CPS doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13254989 Fledge: Benchmarking federated machine learning applications in edge computing systems doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2306.05172 Energy vs Privacy: Estimating the Ecological Impact of Federated Learning doi: 10.1145/3575813.3597344 A survey on efficient federated learning methods for foundation model training doi: arXiv:2401.04472 How Can We Train Deep Learning Models Across Clouds and Continents? An Experimental Study doi: arXiv:2306.03163 A lightweight storage framework for edge computing infrastructures/EdgePersist doi: 10.1016/j.simpa.2023.100549 Dynamic Adaptability in Human-Robot Collaboration for Industrial Assembly: A Behaviour Tree Based Task Execution PlanEMQx: https://github.com/satrai-lab/planemqx</p>

Table 6: Related Strategies and Tasks

Project	Partner(s) participating in this project	Description	Tools	Related Strategies	Related Tasks
FELICE	NTUA, AEGIS, EUNL	Research in collaborative robotics, AI, computer vision, IoT, ML, analytics to create a platform with autonomous, and cognitive technologies. Further improve and accelerate the training process via synthetic data generation in visual inspection tasks and exploit unbiased measures for uncertainty quantification during online execution. Utilise best practices in ethics-by-design principles	(i) Adopt AI-driven autonomous and cognitive technologies; (ii) Utilize computer vision methods to recover the objects in the scene and accelerate the training process (iii) Adopt methods to monitor systems via the integration of heterogeneous sensors and devices in industrial environments; iv) ensure safety, ethics-by-design principles, and lawfulness are respected during the design of the system.	1, 2	2.6, 3.1, 5.1, 5.4
OPENDR	AU	Develops, trains, deploys, and evaluates deep learning models that improve the technical capabilities visual perception tasks.	(i) Take advantage of the OpenDR visual perception methods implemented in the OpenDR toolkit (e.g., CINs) (TRL2/4); (ii) Develop open-source methodological developments and the underlying techniques needed for such CINs	10	4.4
SCOTT	EAB	A pan-European effort with 57 key partners from 12 countries (EU and Brazil), provides comprehensive cost-efficient solutions of wireless, end-to-end secure, trustworthy connectivity and interoperability.	(i) Revise reference architecture that enables interoperability (semantic level) for heterogeneous wireless sensor networks; (ii) Adopt technology and knowledge on AI planning, reinforcement learning, knowledge graphs; (iii) Use ontology and domain modelling to enhance the learning rates of reinforcement learning agents.	3, 7, 9	3.3, 4.2, 6.3, 6.4

<p>INTELLIOT</p>	<p>SAG, STS, DIE</p>	<p>Provides a framework for building local, intelligent IoT/Edge environments that can execute (semi-) autonomous behaviour of “things”, e.g., industrial robots.</p>	<p>(i) Extend semantic models for network configuration to develop simulators that realize digital twins. Allow the generation of infrastructure data (e.g., network and device data), which includes the rare events of failures (<i>TRL 2/4</i>); (ii) Adopt methods for optimally allocating edge apps that run on affected devices in the failed part of the infrastructure.</p>	<p>1, 8, 10</p>	<p>4.3, 5.3</p>
<p>SECOPERA</p>	<p>TSGF, SLC, AEGIS, ITML, DIE, STS</p>	<p>Provides a one stop hub for complex OSS/OSH solutions offering security enhancements for solutions that are integrated in a networked connected environment.</p>	<p>(i) Combine cryptographic and differential privacy techniques to differentiate private data and enable scientists to share useful sensitive data (<i>TRL 2/4</i>); (ii) GDPR e-services, privacy audits and penetration tests, for AIoT complex systems.</p>	<p>7</p>	<p>5.2</p>
<p>SPARTA</p>	<p>IMT</p>	<p>One of the four pilot projects for the ECCC working on the security of the software supply chain, and the privacy in IoT.</p>	<p>Create customisable smart space datasets using SPED semantic models. Event-driven simulation strategies to generate realistic simulated data about the space (events, trajectories, sensor datasets, etc</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>3.1</p>
<p>STAR</p>	<p>SAG, PCL, TSGF</p>	<p>STAR is a joint effort of AI and digital manufacturing experts towards enabling the deployment of standard-based secure, safe reliable and trusted human centric AI systems in manufacturing environments.</p>	<p>(i) Adopt novel technologies that will enable AI systems to acquire knowledge to take timely and safe decisions in dynamic and unpredictable environments; (ii) Leverage synthetic data to improve the accuracy of AI models for visual inspection to accommodate our pursuit to smaller batch sizes; (iii) FL based model to detect anomaly</p>	<p>1, 8</p>	<p>3.1, 4.5</p>

			on IT network flow statistics		
COLLABS	NTUA, SAG, PCL, TSGF, ITML, UNSPMF, STS	An intelligence framework for secure data exchange across the digital supply chain while providing high degree of resilience, reliability, accountability and trustworthiness, focusing on distributed deep learning, anomaly detection, and blockchain technologies.	(i) Develop a system that splits a proposed DL that is meant to do inference at the edge, into layers that are executed to cloud-edge computing continuum considering maximum performance and minimum data transfer (<i>TRL 2/4</i>); (ii) Deploy partially oblivious neural network inference, i.e., using homomorphic encryption, to define the concept of trusted resource domains and mitigate potential privacy issues(<i>TRL 2/4</i>); (iii) Adopt a customizable toolkit for data fusion for multiple modality data streams.	7	4.4 , 5.2
DATABENCH	IDC	Addresses the gap in the current Big Data and AI analytics benchmarking community, by providing certifiable benchmarks.	(i) Leverage business-related benchmarking DataBench studies and results to evaluate and improve PANDORA business intelligence-related tools and achieved outcomes.	6	6.3 , 6.5

AGILEIOT	AU	Develops an agile mobile edge computing framework integrating models of adjustable inference time. It enables collaborative inference of IoT devices and edge servers to maximize the inference accuracy within a delay constraint. (National Funding).	(i) Take advantage of the state-of-the-art dynamic and distributed inference methods developed in AgileIoT project, as well as the insights of joint optimisation of communication and computation gained in AgileIoT project to enable robust AI services for time-critical and mission-critical IoT Applications in Edge-Cloud continuum.	8 , 9	4.5
EXPIDA	CYU	Provides a rich family of explainable methods, tools and causal discovery algorithms to handle imperfect (i.e., inconsistent and/or uncertain) data. (Independent Research Fund of France).	(i) Tools on (explaining) online data streaming analysis, either in a descriptive manner (e.g., through aggregates or other declarative queries) or predictive manner (e.g., unbalanced classification) (TRL4/5); (ii) Develop novel sequential explanations to investigate the true causes for model results, rooted on the data evolving characteristics as well as on the context (domain knowledge)	1 , 3,9	3.3 , 4.2 , 5.1
PARATUS	DLR	Creation of a platform for natural hazard multi-risk assessment	AI-based methods for time series forecasting with uncertainty quantification	2	3.2

<p>GREEN.DAT. AI</p>	<p>AEGIS, STS</p>	<p>GREEN.DAT.AI will demonstrate the efficiencies of the new analytics services in four industries (Smart Energy, Smart Agriculture/Agri- food, Smart Mobility, Smart Banking) and six different application scenarios, leveraging the use of European Data Spaces. The services will cover AI-enabled data enrichment, Incentive mechanisms for Data Sharing, Synthetic Data Generation, Large-scale learning at the Edge/Fog, Federated & Auto ML at the edge/fog, Explainable AI/Feature Learning with Privacy Preservation, Federated & Automatic Transfer Learning, Adaptive FL for Digital Twin Applications, Automated IoT event-based change detection/forecasting.</p>	<p>(i) Powerful data analytics tools (ii) Visualization Tools (iii) Orchestration platform for hyper distributed applications (iv) Large scale analytics and learning (v) Security Mechanisms</p>	<p>3 , 4</p>	<p>3.3 , 3.4 , 4.3 , 5.4</p>
<p>NEMO</p>	<p>AEGIS</p>	<p>NEMO (Next Generation Meta Operating System) will introduce an open source, flexible, adaptable, cybersecure and multi-technology meta- Operating System (mOS). To achieve technology maturity and massive adoption. NEMO aims to establish itself as the game changer of AIoT-Edge-Cloud Continuum by introducing an open source, flexible, adaptable, cybersecure and multi-technology meta-Operating System, sustainable during and after the end of the project, via the Eclipse foundation.</p>	<p>(i) AI meta-Orchestrator (ii) meta Network Cluster controller (iii) Cybersecure Micro-services' Digital Twins (iv) DevZeroOps platform as a Service</p>	<p>1 , 2 , 11</p>	

<p>ASCAPE</p>	<p>UNSPMF, STS</p>	<p>The main objective of ASCAPE is to take advantage of the recent ICT advances in Big Data, Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning to support cancer patients' quality of life and health status. To achieve its objective, ASCAPE will create an open AI infrastructure that will enable health stakeholders (hospitals, research institutions, companies, etc.) to deploy and execute its AI algorithms locally on their private data.</p>	<p>Quality of Life for Cancer Patients, data privacy, federated learning</p>	<p>4 , 7</p>	<p>3.4 , 4.3</p>
<p>C4IIoT</p>	<p>UNSPMF, STS</p>	<p>C4IIoT project will build and demonstrate a novel and unified IIoT cybersecurity framework for malicious and anomalous behaviour anticipation, detection, mitigation, and end-user informing. It will be a holistic and disruptive security-enabling solution to minimise attack surfaces in IIoT systems. The C4IIoT framework will be tested in real settings.</p>	<p>Edge-fog-cloud computing continuum</p>	<p>4 , 7</p>	<p>4.1 , 4.3 , 5.4</p>
<p>I-BiDaaS</p>	<p>UNSPMF</p>	<p>I-BiDaaS aims to empower users to easily utilize and interact with big data technologies, by designing, building, and demonstrating, a unified solution that: significantly increases the speed of data analysis while coping with the rate of data asset growth, and facilitates cross-domain data-flow towards a thriving data-driven EU economy.</p>	<p>Big data analytics and cloud application services</p>	<p>7</p>	<p>4.1</p>

MARVEL	ITML, AEGIS, STS	MARVEL targets the development of a disruptive edge-to-fog-to-cloud computing framework for multi-modal perception and intelligence for audio-visual scene recognition and event detection in a smart city environment.	Data management in edge-fog-cloud continuum	5	3.5 , 5.1
SecDataGen	IMT, TUM	SecDataGen is dedicated to constructing a comprehensive framework to provide secure, trustworthy datasets for smart space ecosystems.	AI-Driven Security Data Synthesis	1	3.1
SYNTHESIS	FRA	Aims to improve the control technology network security in NPP. The project aims to improve the security of network in the sector of power plants, against malware with hidden functions, by the generation of synthetic data and injecting it in the network to study behaviour of attackers.	Investigate whether and how the simulation with a model-based approach for the synthetic generation of network data with hidden malicious code functions for a strategic. Evaluation and validation of the detection and responsiveness of network security mechanisms with regard to malware with hidden functions or modes of action is possible	1,2 , 7	3.1,3.2,4.1
DECENT	FRA	Development of an ICT solution for cross commodity to share and management of energy in smart neighborhoods, linking of different energy resources supported by AI to enable optimal use across building boundaries	Use of AI and blockchain for based testbed for Peer-To-Peer energy trading	4	3.4
ABAC	FRA	It aids the introduction of attribute certificates for data objects describing the security requirement, push/pull model attribute certificates of data objects and role certificates of subjects,		1,3	3.1,3.3

		extension of role based access control.			
ESFR-Simple	STU, FRA	ESFR-SIMPLE is an EU-funded project aiming to improve the safety of the European Sodium Fast Reactor through innovative monitoring, power level flexibility and experimental research.	Propose, develop and assess advanced methods for monitoring and processing operational data using artificial intelligence. Explore of AI applicability in Nuclear engineering	1,3	3.1,3.3
RETENTION	EUNL, STS	RETENTION will provide a platform conceived to support data-driven and AI-assisted clinical decision making, patient monitoring and data-driven management for heart failure patients.	Innovative model driven big data analytics, statistical, artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques		1.5 , 2.6
PHOENI2X	EUNL, STS	PHOENI2X aims to develop a Cyber Resilience Framework providing AI-assisted orchestration, automation & response capabilities for business continuity and recovery, incident response, and information exchange, applying to critical infrastructures.	Amongst other, PHOENI2X will provide valuable insights on assessment models developed to enable assessments & certifications according to specific schemes (e.g., ISO security standards, GDPR, NIS Directive), but also the requirements for Trustworthy AI that PANDORA could leverage.		1.5 , 2.6

<p>SOPRANO</p>	<p>NTUA, AEGIS</p>	<p>SOPRANO aims to advance human robot collaboration in industrial practices by improving context awareness in highly uncertain environments, trustworthy and dependable AI-based techniques for safety monitoring, diagnosis, AI planning and reasoning, and exploiting modular, reconfigurable and flexible engineering tools and techniques to support adaptability, ease of use in various operating environments synthetic data generation, uncertainty quantification, distribution of AI learning and inferencing in the IoTEdge- Cloud continuum</p>	<p>Tools for object perception in uncertain environments for i) generation of synthetic data for training , parametrising signals as continuous functions ii) support improved uncertainty quantification at runtime exploiting the geometric priors and iii) seamless execution of AI components in resource-constrained devices and micro-service orchestration capabilities</p>	<p>1 , 2 , 11</p>	<p>3.1 , 4.5 , 5.1 , 5.4</p>
<p>CONSOLE</p>	<p>CBRL</p>	<p>The CONSOLE project aims to improve cybersecurity in the software development process by enabling automated and real-time testing within a realistic environment, using edge computing technologies and machine learning algorithms. The target is to enhance the security of software applications and systems while reducing costs for SMEs, with a focus on confidentiality, integrity, and availability.</p>	<p>The project provides an automated platform for testing software security, incorporating end-point detection, dynamic analysis, and XR developments.</p>	<p>5 , 6 , 7</p>	<p>3.1 , 3.5 , 6.3 , 6.5</p>

<p>CyberSecDome</p>	<p>CBRL, STS, TUM</p>	<p>CyberSecDome integrates advanced virtual reality with AI-enabled security solutions to enhance the resilience and security of digital infrastructures, facilitating real-time threat prediction and collaborative incident management. The project aims to provide a comprehensive security framework for complex digital systems, ensuring robust incident management and privacy protection.</p>	<p>The project develops AI-driven intrusion detection and incident response mechanisms, leveraging VR to enhance situational awareness and threat intelligence sharing.</p>	<p>7, 8, 10</p>	<p>4.1, 4.3, 4.5, 5.4</p>
<p>SYNAPSE</p>	<p>DIE, FRA, CBRL, EUNL, STS</p>	<p>SYNAPSE delivers a cybersecurity platform with integrated risk management, situational awareness, and incident response capabilities, focusing on both technical and economic risk management. The project aims to establish shared situational awareness and coordinated response among EU member states, with a focus on continuous feedback and standardization.</p>	<p>The platform includes AI-enhanced situational awareness, automated incident response, and smart contract-enabled risk transfer mechanisms. Use of AI for generation of synthetic data</p>	<p>1, 2, 6, 7, 8</p>	<p>4.1, 5.3, 5.5</p>

<p>JIC-GENEO</p>	<p>UNIBO</p>	<p>This project concerns the use of Group Equivariant Non-Expansive Operators (GENEOs) and Topological Data Analysis (TDA) to identify and study patterns in the future technical standard of the sixth-generation technology for wireless communications (6G). Research done in the framework of the CNIT National Laboratory WiLab and the WiLab-Huawei Joint Innovation Center.</p> <p>The project aims to use GENEOs to transparently and efficiently emulate the behavior of an observer interested in identifying relevant patterns in 6G device networks.</p>	<p>Recent developments in the theory of GENEOs and TDA.</p>	<p>3,9</p>	<p>3.3 , 4.2 , 5.5</p>
<p>MobiCM</p>		<p>The aim of the MobiCM research project was to develop a mobile condition monitoring system to monitor production machines in their entirety from just one central measuring point. By disaggregating the sensor data from just one measuring point to individual systems and devices, a comprehensive image of the production system is created with minimal measuring effort. The entirety of the signals is recorded by an active network analysis sensor, which is subsequently attached to a network distribution point or a network connection point.</p>			

Annex B

Table 7: Related Papers

Paper	Data Type	Conference	Date	Contribution	Limitation
Openshs: Open smart home simulator [ASC17]	ADL data	Sensors 17.5	2017	3D model-based open-source tool, has statistical learning or interaction method for generation, simulates the interactions between physical entities like person, sensors, and network entities like accessing point. The pattern of all entities is used as application domain knowledge, performed in pre-defined scripts or inputs from GUI.	Massive manually setting for scenario configuration.
Persim 3D: Context-driven simulation and modeling of human activities in smart spaces [LCL15]	ADL data	IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering	2015	3D model-based tool generation based on statistic learning of a seed dataset, simulates the interactions between physical entities like person, sensors, and network entities like accessing point. Distributions of entities in the physical world are used as application knowledge.	Only use a statistical model to capture ADL data, lack of capture for fine-grain interaction of occupant and the environment. Not open-source causes less flexibility for usage.
The creation of simulated activity datasets using a graphical intelligent environment simulation tool [SCN14]	ADL data	International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society	2014	2D graph-based tool with rapid data generation based on statistical learning of a seed dataset, simulates interaction between physical entities like person, sensors, and network entities like accessing point.	2D representation, lack of dimension of the scenario. Only uses a statistical model, lacks fine-grain interaction data.
Exploring city digital twins as policy tools: A task-based approach to generating synthetic data on urban mobility [PY21]	ADL data	Data & Policy 3	2021	A framework with city digital twin and manually set tasks to simulate citizen activity data on a large scale, focusing on modeling physical attributes with specific tasks as application domain knowledge.	Lack of network-level abstraction, massive manual setting for scenario configuration is needed, especially for

					larger scales like a city.
MoSIoT: Modeling and simulating IoT healthcare-monitoring systems for people with disabilities [MNL21]	Healthcare monitor signal	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	2021	A framework using the semantic model to build a relationship between different devices in a healthcare system, focusing on modeling physical data of patients and sensors, with application response to physical data.	Only dedicated to Healthcare-Monitor systems, cannot modify to other data.
The ns-3 Network Simulator [RH10]	Network traffic	Modeling and Tools for Network Simulation	2010	An open-sourced discrete-event network simulator for realistic network traffic simulation, using the script to build the semantic graph of entities in networks and simulates based on configuration and protocols applied on them.	Manual settings for network topologies are needed.
Smartspec: Customizable smart space datasets via event-driven simulations [CJG22]	Occupancy data and Sensor data	PerCom	2022	A framework using the semantic model to generate realistic occupancy data, with customizable sensor data generation at the physical and network level.	State-of-the-art for occupancy data generation, the user has to define the sensor data generation function.
Soundspaces 2.0: A simulation platform for visual-acoustic learning [CSG22]	Acoustic signal	Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems	2022	A geometry-based framework for audio rendering in 3D environments, generating realistic acoustics for arbitrary sounds captured from arbitrary microphone locations, focusing on physical-level sensory data.	State-of-the-Art acoustic signal simulation, yet needs to manually provide a 3D model of the scenario. Dedicated to acoustic signals.
Lidarsim: Realistic lidar simulation by leveraging the real world [MWW20]	Point cloud	Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition	2020	A 3D model-based framework simulates point cloud captured by Lidar based on Raytracing, focusing on realistic sensor data at the physical level.	Simulation scenario needs manual setting. Dedicated to Lidar sensor and point cloud, hard to transfer to other modality data.
Optimal rough terrain trajectory generation for wheeled mobile robots [HK07]	Robot trajectory	The International Journal of Robotics Research	2007	A framework solving the optimal trajectory for wheeled robots on uneven terrains, with consideration for the	Dedicated to robot trajectories, hard to transfer to other modality data. This method

				constraints of the robot, like speed limits, turning angle constraints, and ground friction coefficients.	does not consider possible collisions with obstacles, which limits its usage.
Trajectory Generation for Mobile Robots in a Dynamic Environment using Nonlinear Model Predictive Control [BHK21]	Robot trajectory	International Conference on Automation Science and Engineering	2021	A framework using Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) and differential equations for robots and constraints to generate non-collision trajectories for robots in real-time. Physical data is conveyed by equations and mathematical models, further solved by NMPC algorithms.	Dedicated to robot trajectories, hard to transfer to other modality data.
Synthetic data with nested Markov chain for CIMA-based smart lighting control deployment simulation [PAP23]	Sensor data	ICoICT	2023	The framework leverages nested Markov Chain to synthesize data on lighting control systems, which is used as a data augmentation method performed on physical data of lighting devices to improve further usage for higher applications.	Modeling the complex interactions in a CIMA environment can be challenging and computationally intensive. Ensuring that the simulation results can be generalized to real-world deployments is difficult. Lack of modeling on network-level data.
Machine learning methods and synthetic data generation to predict large wildfires [PTC21]	Sensor data	Sensors 21.11	2021	The framework proposes a method that combines machine learning methods with synthetic data generation on physical features to improve the accuracy and reliability of wildfire prediction applications. The synthesis method is based on random sampling over different features related to wildfire events using a Markov process.	The selection of features and probability of the Markov chain is sensitive due to a lack of data in wildfire events.
Wasserstein generative adversarial	Image (physical)	PMLR	2017	Generative adversarial networks (GAN) use 2 networks (generator and	Training costs are large for GAN, both in terms of

networks [ACB17]				discriminator) to compete with each other and generate high-quality images, using the Wasserstein distance to control the balance between the generator and discriminator.	computing resources and time. Additionally, GAN doesn't perform well on large-scale images.
High-resolution image synthesis with latent diffusion models [RBL22]	Image (physical)	CVPR	2022	Stable Diffusion combines 2 successive networks for the tasks of compression/decompression and generation, which significantly reduces computational resource needs while maintaining high image quality and resolution. The model introduces a cross-attention mechanism, linking text-to-image, allowing for image generation based on text descriptions.	The time and memory cost of generation in the diffusion method is relatively high, making it more costly than other generation methods.
Grid Diffusion Models for Text-to-Video Generation [LKK24]	Video (physical)	CVPR	2024	Grid-Diffusion leverages pre-trained image generation models to generate keyframes of a video and then interpolates frames in between, maintaining high efficiency for video generation.	The model relies on a pre-trained text-to-image model and does not directly train on videos, failing to exploit the rich information in video content.
Free-bloom: Zero-shot text-to-video generator with LLM director and LDM animator [HFS24]	Video (physical)	NeurIPS	2024	Free-bloom combines LLM and Diffusion models to generate videos with guidance from a pre-trained LLM, maintaining consistency during the video generation process and enabling generation without specific target data.	The model relies on a pre-trained text-to-image model and LLM, which may inherit the biases and limitations of the pre-trained model.
Make-it-3d: High-fidelity 3D creation from a single image with diffusion prior [TWZ23]	Point Cloud (physical)	CVPR	2023	Make-It-3D leverages prior knowledge from a trained 2D diffusion model to act as 3D-aware supervision for 3D creation. The diffusion model generates multiple views from one front view of objects and then performs 3D creation	The model does not work well with occluded situations, which are prevalent in reality.

				based on multiple-view information. The texture of the 3D point cloud can also be generated from multiple-view images.	
Zero-1-to-3: Zero-shot one image to 3D object [LWH23]	3D triangle mesh (physical)	CVPR	2023	Zero-1-to-3 fine-tunes the pre-trained large diffusion model, like Stable Diffusion, on synthetic 3D view images, and then performs 3D reconstruction to obtain a 3D triangle mesh.	The model relies on a pre-trained text-to-image model and LLM, which may convey the same biases and limitations of the pre-trained model. It is based on a large-scale diffusion model, which is costly in terms of time and memory during training and generation.
GAN-based data augmentation strategy for sensor anomaly detection in industrial robots [LDQ21]	Sensor data	Sensors Journal	2021	A framework using GAN to augment data to improve sensor anomaly detection in industrial robots. The framework processes sensor data to generate normal and abnormal samples for use in successive applications.	The model is trained based on specific sensor types; any change in sensor devices requires retraining the model. Lack of flexibility.
SudokuSens: Enhancing Deep Learning Robustness for IoT Sensing Applications using a Generative Approach [WLK23]	Sensor data	Sensys	2023	SudokuSens leverages a Conditional VAE model to generate synthetic data based on collected seed data, which greatly improves the performance of machine learning applications based on this augmented dataset.	Some data collection is still needed as seed data. Models are trained based on specific sensor types; any change in sensor devices requires retraining the model.
Wi-fi see it all: generative adversarial network-augmented versatile wi-fi imaging [LLY20]	Sensor data	Sensys	2020	A framework using GAN to generate images and enhance the Wi-Fi imaging system. The GAN model takes blurry or incomplete images from the system (calculated from radio reflection) and generates enhanced images using the GAN generator.	Computational complexity is high. The impact of environmental changes on imaging accuracy is a concern.

Synthetic attack data generation model applying generative adversarial network for intrusion detection [KS23]	Network Intrusion data / Application label data	Computers & Security	2023	A framework using GAN to generate realistic intrusion event labels on network data, benefiting other applications trained based on generated data, showing the potential of synthetic data in IoT network scenarios.	Lack of ability for user configuration, as the model only learns from a seed dataset.
SYN-GAN: A robust intrusion detection system using GAN-based synthetic data for IoT security [RPM24]	Network Intrusion data / Application label data	Internet of Things	2024	A framework using GAN to generate realistic intrusion event labels on network data, showing that only synthetic data can support network intrusion detection machine learning applications for IoT security.	Lack of ability for user configuration, as the model only learns from a seed dataset.
GFL: Federated learning on non-IID data via privacy-preserving synthetic data [CZL23]	Sensor / image data	PerCom	2023	A framework using GAN with differential privacy to generate synthetic data to help federated learning algorithms overcome the challenge of data heterogeneity.	Differential privacy will significantly degrade performance. The framework is evaluated on a simple dataset, which is not fully examined.
Timevae: A variational auto-encoder for multivariate time series generation [DFW21]	Time series data	ICLR	2021	A framework using a VAE model with a designed Convolution Neural Network (CNN) block to capture trend and seasonal features in time series.	Lacks the ability to capture relationships across variables. The user cannot configure the model during the generation process.
Time-Transformer: Integrating Local and Global Features for Better Time Series Generation [LWL24]	Time series data	SIAM International Conference on Data Mining	2024	A framework that combines CNN and Transformer to capture short-term and long-term relationships, generating time series data with higher realism.	Relatively high time complexity for training and generation. The user cannot configure the model during the generation process.
Social-Interaction GAN: Pedestrian Trajectory Prediction [ZWD21]	Trajectory image data	International Conference on Wireless Algorithms, Systems, and Applications	2021	A framework that generates pedestrian trajectory in image formation based on a top-view image, demonstrating the ability of deep learning models to capture activity	Only tested on people; generalization to other types of devices in IoT is uncertain.

				patterns through images.	
Informer: Beyond efficient transformer for long sequence time-series forecasting [ZZP21]	Time series data	AAAI conference on artificial intelligence	2021	A framework capturing long-term relationships in time using the Transformer network, demonstrating the strong ability of the self-attention mechanism.	Not designed to capture cross-variable relationships. Users cannot configure the model directly.
Spectral temporal graph neural network for multivariate time-series forecasting [CWD20]	Time series data	NeurIPS	2020	A framework using Graph Neural Networks (GNN) to build spatial relationships, with the ability to perform accurate predictions on time series data. The GNN provides a dependency graph, which has some interpretability for humans.	Although the model shows a strong ability for prediction, the gap between generation and prediction remains. Users cannot configure the model directly.
Crossformer: Transformer utilizing cross-dimension dependency for multivariate time series forecasting [ZY23]	Time series data	ICLR	2023	A framework leveraging two successive transformer blocks to learn the time domain pattern and spatial domain pattern respectively, showing strong performance on time series prediction.	Relatively high computing time complexity compared to other methods. The gap between generation and prediction. Users cannot configure the model directly.
Rf genesis: Zero-shot generalization of mmwave sensing through simulation-based data synthesis and generative diffusion models [CZ23]	Radio frequency signal	Sensys	2023	A framework leveraging Large Language Models (LLM) and Vision Large Models (VLM) to generate appropriate 3D scenarios, then simulate based on the 3D model to generate the final sensor signal. The model effectively integrates different modalities of the 3D model and language, eliminating the need for heavy manual configuration problems seen in other simulation methods.	The simulation part of the framework is dedicated to radio frequency, which is hard to generalize to other types of data.